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Master-Arbeit

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Master of Science

Loosely-coupled data-intensive Simulation
of X-Ray Scattering from Plasmas
in an HPC workflow using ADIOS2

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Task

The objective of this Master's thesis is to enable, test and evaluate in-memory staging with high performance computing (HPC) applications. Particle-in-Cell (PIC) data, created by the massively scalable code PIconGPU, will be staged to a significantly smaller application trying to avoid backlog from classical file-based post-processing. Using the ADIOS2 IO library and the openPMD API – a library that allows to describe PIC data and can communicate with ADIOS2 –, F. Pöschel will develop a framework to loosely couple HPC applications in a producer/consumer workflow where transferred, high-throughput data is kept in memory and never written to disk.

With this framework, the student will implement staging in a concrete workflow with data flowing from PIconGPU (data source) to the scattering code GAPD (data sink), both ad libitum runnable on either CPU or GPU hardware.

He will identify the parameters of such a simulation and devise a strategy to optimize, test, analyze and explain resulting runtime behaviors.

Next to documenting the aforementioned tasks and implementation, the written report will also analyze existing literature and state-of-the-art workflows in the HPC community.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die von mir am heutigen Tag dem Prüfungsausschuss der Fakultät für Informatik eingereichte Masterarbeit zum Thema:

Loosely coupled data-intensive simulation of X-Ray Scattering
from Plasmas in an HPC workflow using ADIOS2

vollkommen selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt sowie Zitate kenntlich gemacht habe.

Dresden, den 18. Dezember 2019

Franz Pöschel

Abstract

The openPMD API is a DSL used in plasma physical simulations for the description of particle-mesh data according to the openPMD standard. The API offers a number of flexibly interchangeable efficient implementations in terms of IO backends. Having initially been designed with file-based IO in mind, we intend to overcome filesystem bottlenecks by enabling a streaming-aware description of particle-mesh data. The streaming backend is provided by the ADIOS2 framework, currently in development at Oak Ridge National Laboratory.

Extended this way, we use the openPMD API to loosely couple a simulation computed by PIconGPU – a hardware accelerated implementation of the particle-in-cell algorithm developed at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf – with an analysis computed by GAPD, which is a hardware-accelerated atom-based polychromatic diffraction simulation.

In loose coupling, as opposed to tight coupling, two (or more) applications are executed in separate, but cooperate by exchanging data. This way, we want to make use of heterogeneous hardware more flexibly and allow for standalone codes instead of plugins, using a unified streaming-aware API for particle-mesh data and leveraging high-speed communication infrastructure available in modern compute clusters.

We put the coupled simulation to testing on the Taurus compute cluster located at TU Dresden, comparing several execution strategies. When communicating between codes via RDMA networks implemented through Infiniband, we measure that the time performance by data dumps settles between that of filesystem IO and that of raw simulation performance. Scaling behavior depends on the chosen execution strategy.

Kurzfassung

Die openPMD API ist eine DSL, die in plasmaphysikalischen Simulationen für die Beschreibung von Partikel-Mesh-Daten nach dem openPMD-Standard verwendet wird. Die API bietet mehrere effiziente Implementierungen durch IO-Backends, welche nach Bedarf flexibel angewählt und ausgetauscht werden können. Nachdem die ursprüngliche Gestaltung der API ihren Fokus auf dateisystembasiertes IO legte, zielt diese Arbeit darauf ab, im Dateisystem entstehende Flaschenhälse durch eine Beschreibung von Partikel-Mesh-Daten mit Streaming-Semantik zu umgehen. Das Backend hierfür wird vom ADIOS2-Framework bereitgestellt, welches derzeit am Oak Ridge National Laboratory entwickelt wird.

Die hiermit erweiterte openPMD API nutzen wir, um eine Simulation, welche durch PIconGPU berechnet wird – einer hardwarebeschleunigten Implementierung des Particle-in-Cell-Algorithmus – lose mit einer durch GAPD berechneten Analy-

se zu koppeln, welches eine hardwarebeschleunigte atom-basierte polychromatische Beugungssimulation berechnet.

Zwei oder mehr lose gekoppelte Applikationen werden im Gegensatz zu eng gekoppelten Applikationen separat ausgeführt und kooperieren miteinander durch Datenaustausch. Das erlaubt eine flexiblere Ausnutzung heterogener Hardware ebenso wie die Nutzung selbstständiger Codes im Gegensatz zu Plugins. Wir erreichen dies durch eine API mit Streaming-Semantik für Partikel-Mesh-Daten und durch Ausnutzung von Hochgeschwindigkeitskommunikationsinfrastruktur, welche auf modernen Rechenclustern verfügbar ist.

Wir führen Tests mit mehreren Ausführungsstrategien auf dem an der TU Dresden befindlichen Rechencluster Taurus durch. Bei Kommunikation zwischen Codes über RDMA-Netze, die durch Infiniband implementiert sind, messen wir eine Zeitperformanz, welche sich zwischen der Performanz von Dateisystem-IO und derjenigen der eigentlichen Simulation ohne IO ansiedelt. Das Skalierungsverhalten hängt stark von der gewählten Ausführungsstrategie ab.

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Chapter 1

Introduction and state of the art

A recent topic in high-performance computing (HPC) that is expected to increase in relevance in future years is the IO bottleneck. GPU hardware is continuing to reshape the compute landscape found in the TOP500 list [28]. HPC applications scalable up to modern-day supercomputers can exploit the computing power of hundreds of GPUs in parallel. Such an application is PIconGPU, an electromagnetic particle-in-cell code developed mainly at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, that can process up to 60 GB per compute node [6], achieved through a performance-portable accelerator implementation via the Alpaka [41] accelerator abstraction library.

With simulations amassing ever-increasing amounts of data per second, traditional methods for further processing of such data are coming to their limits. IO routines in PIconGPU are still implemented in terms of plugins writing data to and loading data from the filesystem. While simulations often exhibit near-ideal compute-side weak scaling behavior, scaling capabilities of conventional filesystem-based IO are limited by parallel bandwidths as well as by filesystem capacities. In effect, compute performance is throttled by the incapability to further process the amassed data fast enough, voiding progress achieved in computing performance through the use of accelerator hardware.

These massive amounts of data do not solely pose a technical challenge, from the domain scientist’s perspective this raw data also presents a relatively low informational yield, necessitating data extraction through adequate analysis tools. In a loosely coupled workflow, these two (or more) stages in a computational simulation are performed by different applications launched as different processes on the system. The term “loose coupling” stands in contrast with tightly coupled applications that integrate several heterogeneous stages of a simulation/analysis/visualization/accumulation workflow into a monolithic integrated application.

Since from the scientist’s perspective, persistent storage of intermediate raw

data is in general not necessary in a loosely coupled setup and from the perspective of the IO system, it is not feasible, streaming workflows are used to face these challenges. This way, we attempt to overcome an intrinsic performance challenge in loosely coupled simulations stemming from the necessity to perform IO between single components.

A streaming workflow will allow making better use of the benefits coming with a loosely coupled approach, which can be described by *developer flexibility* and *hardware flexibility*. With developer flexibility, we denote the increased reusability of standalone tools e.g. for analysis and visualization as opposed to the complexity of large monolithic applications. Scientific workflows can adopt loosely coupled workflows to enable rapid prototyping. With hardware flexibility, we denote the opportunity to decouple simulation code from hardware and IO description. While in tightly coupled applications, making use of increasingly heterogeneous hardware is mostly possible only if explicitly encoded into the source code, mapping loosely coupled components to available hardware in an adaptable manner comes naturally with a loosely coupled approach.

This can help underutilization of allocated resources, as for example the use of a lower number of GPUs than available per compute node since host-side memory is also needed for computations performed by CPUs. The hardware perspective of loose coupling is the separate execution of applications that can potentially happen also on different compute partitions, allowing to allocate resources on a per-component base. This approach again necessitates IO between components.

Since we stressed developer flexibility as an advantage found in loose coupling, we intend to not make streaming workflows an additional burden on developers as opposed to filesystem-based IO routines. For streaming in the domain of plasma physics, we will attempt to pursue this objective by use of the openPMD API [20, 25] and the ADIOS2 framework [19]. The openPMD API is a domain-specific library for data description along the openPMD standard for particle-mesh data, amassed in numerous physical simulations. This data description is implemented efficiently in terms of interchangeable backends. During this Master's Thesis, we will implement the ADIOS2 backend, where ADIOS2 is a generic IO framework with parallel HPC applications as a first-class use case currently under development at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory.

The openPMD API currently provides only implementations in terms of filesystem-based IO backends. The implementation of the ADIOS2 backend will leverage streaming capabilities provided by this framework next to filesystem-based IO, with further extension towards data description for use within one process without performing IO being in reach. We extend the interface of the openPMD API with a streaming-aware description for data movement and implement this generic description in terms of the concrete ADIOS2 backend.

Thus extending the openPMD API, we use it as the component of a simulation software stack in plasma physics that makes the flexibility of loose coupling available to scientists and developers, while still allowing to express data within a straightforward notation in the problem domain.

With this streaming software stack at hand, we will put it to testing by setting up a coupled simulation with PIConGPU as a data source and GAPD [13], a diffraction simulation code, as a data sink. PIConGPU currently performs IO in terms of directly writing to ADIOS [27] or HDF5 [33] and implements IO such that it is restricted to filesystem-based workflows. We implement a streaming-aware openPMD plugin in PIConGPU that will in functionality encompass both legacy plugins, while reaping at the same time benefits of new backends becoming available in the openPMD API, such as the ADIOS2 backend that will see development over the course of this Master’s Thesis as well. GAPD on the other hand, while also scaling to multi-GPU clusters, reads data from various text file formats. By implementing an openPMD routine for input reading, we get possible performance improvements on two levels: With filesystem-based IO, improvement is reached through IO from binary formats. With streaming-based IO, improvement is reached through avoidance of the file system.

The structure of this Thesis is as follows. In chapter 2, we present previous work upon which we build our streaming software stack. This includes the openPMD API, ADIOS2 as well as the two coupled applications, PIConGPU and GAPD. In chapter 3, we will then describe the streaming workflow that we add to the openPMD API, together with its concrete implementation in terms of ADIOS2. Chapter 4 will concern itself with making use of such a streaming-enabled data description library for building a concrete coupled workflow between PIConGPU and GAPD. We will evaluate this coupled workflow in chapter 5 and compare different strategies for execution. Finally, we draw conclusions and give an outlook on future research in chapter 6.

In the remainder of this chapter, we give an overview of previous work and research on loose coupling.

Fox, Jha and Ramakrishnan [16] categorize streaming workflows into different paradigms. They name:

multiple loosely-coupled tasks A possibly large number of independently executing heterogeneous tasks communicate with one another.

MapReduce This paradigm has seen wide-spread adoption in big data analysis and generalizes a typical use case where data is first processed independently and then “shuffled” in a collective operation.

Bulk synchronous parallel This paradigm model, first defined by Valiant [35], conceptualizes parallelism by having distributed computation components that

communicate via a routing network. This corresponds to distributed memory as opposed to shared memory.

Dataflow Streaming is defined by the flow of data through single components that transform input streams into output streams.

Streaming HPC Data being amassed by simulations is iteratively fed into analysis tools.

We note that “streaming” is found at different levels of an application setup depending on the paradigm and a single such setup may exhibit several kinds of such paradigms. For our use case, the internal parallelism of single applications is implemented in terms of the *message passing interface* (MPI, [15]) that follows the *bulk synchronous parallel* model. Our focus, however, rests on streaming from PIconGPU to GAPD which falls under the categories *multiple loosely-coupled tasks* as well as *streaming HPC*.

Loose coupling frameworks have seen a rise in recent years. Well-known and established are the task-based Python framework DASK [10] as well as the Map-Reduce-based JVM-framework Apache Spark [38]. While Apache Spark sees main usage in the domain of Big Data analysis, DASK positions itself as a framework with lower-level primitives, allowing for a wider range of applications. Within the categories above, its approach is to couple *multiple loosely-coupled tasks* via the definition of a fine-grained task-graph, yielding an acyclic *dataflow*. Applications include typical HPC problems, such as Machine Learning and simulations. The role of DASK in these applications is to provide for a logical and declarative description of the steps necessary to solve the problem at hand in the form of a task graph. A mapping to the available hardware will then be computed by the chosen Dask Scheduler, alleviating developers from implementing hardware-aware problem descriptions manually.

Within the domain of Big Data Analysis, many more frameworks are to be found for data streaming. Apache Kafka [18] provides a server or a cluster of several servers that applications can write to and read from. The server hereby takes a role comparable to a database, leveraging database technology to streaming workflows. Apache Flink [17] can be categorized as a dataflow framework, enabling parallel and pipelined processing. Apache Storm [39] builds upon acyclic task graphs to process unbounded amounts of data in realtime. Apache Hadoop [36] provides for an integrated big-data streaming framework, encompassing a distributed filesystem, a framework for managing resources as well as a scalable implementation of the MapReduce paradigm to make use of these components.

Taking a similar perspective as the DASK framework, Boehm et al. [2] describe a typical loose coupling scenario using a task-based parallelism approach. Unlike

DASK, where all tasks reside within the encompassing DASK framework, this approach considers each such task a separate application, executed within the boundaries of a compute cluster’s batch system. This work focuses hence on the design of a batch system where loosely coupled execution is a first-class use case, as opposed to the batch systems commonly in use today that favor the execution of a low number of tightly-coupled applications with high application-level parallelism over the execution of a large number of applications with less scaling potential per application.

The authors mention that a typical loosely-coupled application workflow will have little to no communication between single applications. This can be explained with the fact that communication is naturally more cost-efficient within one application – where communication is optimally zero-cost by directly accessing another program part’s data buffers – as opposed to communication across application boundaries where copying of data becomes mandatory.

Nonetheless, certain loosely-coupled scientific applications hold a need for large-scale communication between single components in execution and hardware for fast inter-process communication, such as Infiniband, Cray Portals/Gemini, IBM DCMF, etc. is gaining increasing relevance. Driven by necessity on the one hand, and the availability of suitable hardware on the other hand, frameworks for loose coupling with massive data exchange between single components have seen creation. This includes the ADIOS [27] framework, whose rewrite in version 2 [19] is the framework of choice for the implementation of this Master’s Thesis.

The position of this Thesis within these frameworks is not that of a competing standard, but rather does it intend to be an instance of the typical use cases. We describe and develop a framework for building a communication link between two or more plasma physical simulations, analyses, visualizations, data aggregations, etc. that produce or consume data describable by the openPMD meta standard. By using a description that aims to be expressive within the problem domain and at the same time flexible within the hardware and implementation domain, we propose a solution that meets the flexibility requirements of loose coupling frameworks while at the same time allowing experimenters to describe their data in a natural notation.

Generic code couplers targeted for use also in scientific simulations include the frameworks MpCCI [23] as well as openPalm [30, 4]. Both of these leverage available implementations of the message passing interface (MPI) to enable the streaming of data. Intending to be an all-in-one solution for code coupling, openPalm additionally provides the capability for the orchestration of coupled codes. Indeed, the original motivation for this framework has been a concrete use case (oceanographic data assimilation) where dynamic coupling was necessary, i.e. the configuration of the single coupled components could not be statically known upfront. Piacentini et al. [30] mention that the orchestration of such a coupled simulation could turn out to be

a bottleneck in massively parallel codes. Jauré, Duchaine and Gicquel [22] detect a similar scaling issue with the architecture of MpCCI that relies on a central control process to monitor the execution of single codes.

They take this as an incentive to explore technical foundations for a *direct communication scheme*, allowing to couple codes without making use of a central communication bridge that could serve as a bottleneck. Cecchis, Drummond and Castillo [7] describe the *Distributed Coupling Toolkit*, where distributed coupling denotes exactly this approach at code coupling where no central coupler is required.

Opposing the notion of direct communication from source to sink, attempts have been made at making central message brokers scale not by eliminating them, but by exploring parallel architectures for such middleware. From the domain of Big Data analysis, we have previously mentioned Apache Kafka. A framework for “extreme-scale data management” taking a similar approach targeted at usage in HPC applications is found in DataSpaces [11] which provides for a distributed data service that applications can subscribe to for writing and reading. This framework sees optional support from ADIOS2 via implementation as a transport engine.

Given the presented abundance of streaming platforms, the necessity arises to decouple simulation code from the description of data movement in order to allow for usage of single applications flexibly within different frameworks. This Thesis explores the description of data and of data movement within the domain of particle-mesh data in a way that allows for flexible choice of interoperability with other codes while efficiently making use of recent technology trends.

Chapter 2

Fundamentals

This Thesis builds upon a stack of existing software and standards. Before going into detail about the additions from this Thesis, we will shortly present this previous work. We begin with the openPMD API [25] and ADIOS2 [19] which we both use to build a domain-specific description for data amassed in plasma physical simulations with streaming-aware semantics. After this, we present PIconGPU [5] and GAPD [13], tools used for performing plasma-physical simulation and analysis respectively. We will later use these tools to put the streaming framework to use by building a prototype simulation workflow.

2.1 Particle-mesh data and the openPMD standard

Particle-mesh data Many simulations in computational plasma physics, such as the widely-used particle-in-cell algorithm, work on data in the form of particles and meshes. Hereby, a mesh is an n -dimensional (mostly $n \in \{2, 3\}$) grid, describing a field (often electric or magnetic fields) by splitting a known n -dimensional space into discrete chunks, so-called *cells*. Each such cell's physical quantities are then given as an n -dimensional vector.

Particle-mesh based algorithms describe particle data contained spatially in such cells. This particle data consist of single particles that are given by their n -dimensional location in the observed space. A particle might hereby be a so-called macro-particle, corresponding with possibly a large number of actual particles.

Next to the aforementioned heavy-weight data, further mostly lightweight data may be used to describe other physical properties, including for example particle or mesh types (e.g. electrons, ions, atom types, electric or magnetic fields), particle masses, used units, etc.

This approach at modeling physical data is less compute-heavy than particle-particle approaches that rely solely on interaction between particles, but allows at the same time to examine small-scale particle effects that would be averaged out in a mesh-only simulation.

openPMD The ambition of the openPMD meta standard [20] is to ease the collaboration between simulation and analysis tools that process particle-mesh data in the described layout. This standard describes the logical layout of particle-mesh data in a clearly-defined hierarchical structure, while at the same time staying backend agnostic to allow for implementations in different physical storage formats as required by the user.

In the following, we will describe fundamental concepts of the openPMD meta-data standard. openPMD is a hierarchical standard, a single non-leaf element in the hierarchy is a **group** (analogous to folders in file systems). Note that the description is conceptual and non-exhaustive, for a complete definition please refer to the technical files at [20].

Attributes Groups, as well as the actual datasets may be complemented with attributes. Attributes are lightweight metadata, often consisting of single numerical values, but also allowing to store string data or numerical vectors. The openPMD standard requires a number of attributes, for example to describe the SI unit of a physical quantity. Other than the required attributes, custom attributes may also be defined if considered useful in an application.

Iterations Iterations form the top-most layer of the openPMD data hierarchy. Since a simulation may produce not only one single snapshot, but rather any number of temporal snapshots, openPMD allows organizing data into iterations (also “time steps”). The complete hierarchy, including all iterations, is referred to as a **Series**. One iteration is a self-contained group in the openPMD hierarchy, describing all necessary data and metadata partaking in this iteration. As a result, all time steps are independent of one another and one time step within the same openPMD Series may contain different types of particle species or meshes.

Records Records are special groups in the hierarchy used to store physical quantities, mesh- and particle data alike. Each record contains a number of **record components**, storing the heavyweight payload in the form of multidimensional datasets/arrays.

Meshes Each iteration bundles its contained meshes into one subgroup, usually named “meshes” or “fields”. Each mesh is a record contained in that group. Let E be a 3-dimensional mesh describing an electric field. The mesh record will

contain three record components, typically (but not necessarily) referred to as x , y and z . Each such component will store one dimension of the vectors that make up the mesh in a 3-dimensional dataset. As an example, to reconstruct the vector describing the electric field in cell $(0, 0, 0)$, we need to index into all three datasets x , y and z , each at position $(0, 0, 0)$.

Particles Analogous to meshes, each iteration has one group for its contained particle species. Each particle species is *not* itself a record, but a container of records. Two required records for each particle species are “position” and “positionOffset” which together describe the position of particles – with the possibility to split in two for numerical reasons. Assuming again a three-dimensional physical space, such a record will usually consist of the record components x , y and z . Since there is no grid-like structure for particle data, the particles are simply “listed” sequentially and each such component is hence one-dimensional, regardless of the space’s dimensionality.

As an example, the full hierarchy for the record components of a mesh E at iteration 1200 may look like in the following:

```
/data/1200/fields/E/x
/data/1200/fields/E/y
/data/1200/fields/E/z
```

Each of those components is a matrix of same dimensionality and extent per dimension.

Likewise, for a particle species e , its mandatory record components will be of the form:

```
/data/1200/particles/e/position/x
/data/1200/particles/e/positionOffset/x
/data/1200/particles/e/position/y
/data/1200/particles/e/positionOffset/y
/data/1200/particles/e/position/z
/data/1200/particles/e/positionOffset/z
```

These datasets are one-dimensional arrays, again each of the same size. While splitting positional data into an offset and a precise value with respect to that offset is interesting in many applications for numerical reasons, not all applications actually want to make use of this. In order to avoid storing needless data, a record component may also be *constant*, i.e. given by its extent and a constant value that is found at all possible indices.

The openPMD API: An implementation of the openPMD standard The openPMD standard is intentionally a *meta* standard and abstains from defining a concrete implementation. It describes not the actual binary or textual format used for storage, but rather the data layout within such a format. Such a storage format should be able to provide for a number of basic facilities in order to store particle-mesh data according to the openPMD standard:

Hierarchies The storage format should be able to represent the openPMD meta format’s hierarchical layout of nested groups.

Datasets The format must allow storing the heavyweight physical data in the form of matrices with arbitrary dimension.

Attributes The openPMD standard uses lightweight attributes, associated with hierarchical groups as well as datasets.

All of the entities listed above should be identified by unique strings within their respective contexts.

Since the openPMD standard imposes an equivalent logical description of data regardless of the chosen storage system at hand, the openPMD API [25] has emerged. This API builds upon two core concepts:

1. Allow for a straightforward description of particle-mesh data according to the openPMD standard in an easy-to-use application programmer interface for C++ and Python.
2. Flexibly let the user choose a preferred backend for storage on the file system, independently of the data description.

The openPMD API currently implements the backends HDF5 [33], ADIOS [27] and JSON. The implementation of the ADIOS2 [19] backend forms part of this Master’s thesis. While the HDF5 and both versions of the ADIOS backends are useful for scalable data movement in high-performance computations, the JSON backend is intended for prototyping purposes where a backend needs to be easy to install and easily human-readable rather than scalable for massive amounts of data.

Independently of the chosen backend, the openPMD API allows users to switch between two different data layouts:

file-based Every iteration forms a file of its own. Take notice that the concrete meaning of the word *file* depends on the implementation within the backend and may also refer physically to a folder.

group-based All data is collected into one single file and iterations are modeled using hierarchical groups the same way as for meshes and particles.

Unfortunately, this terminology clashes with the distinction between *streaming-based* and *file(system)-based* workflows. We will refer to the latter as **disk-based** workflows in the remainder of this Thesis for clarity purposes.

2.2 ADIOS2

The ADIOS2 (*adaptable IO system*) framework [19], developed mainly at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory, in collaboration with Kitware Inc., Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Georgia Institute of Technology and Rutgers University, has set its target as fully replacing the legacy ADIOS framework in version 1 [27]. For clarity purposes, we will refer to the latter framework as ADIOS1.

The ADIOS framework in both versions is intended as a flexible approach at implementing IO routines in HPC applications. ADIOS1 has seen usage in numerous applications from this field, including as a plugin for PIconGPU and as a backend for the openPMD API, both of relevance for this Master’s Thesis.

With ADIOS1 having been written as a C API with optional Fortran bindings, ADIOS2 has been written from scratch in modern C++11 with a focus on having a modular and extensible architecture. Optional language bindings are provided for Python, C, Fortran, and Matlab. In days of increasing hardware heterogeneity, a major feature of interest are the concrete IO implementations in the backend of the framework, referred to as *transport method* in ADIOS1 and as *engine* in ADIOS2. [quote ADIOS2 paper] lists “[e]xascale computing, Big Data, Internet of Things (IoT), Burst Buffers, High Bandwidth Memory (HBM) [and] Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA)” as some of the topical techniques taken into consideration for the design of the engines in ADIOS2.

Data is described in the ADIOS2 framework in terms of *attributes* and *variables* and consumed in terms of *steps*. We describe briefly the meaning of these terms.

attributes Among variables and attributes, attributes are more restricted in usage.

They are used to store simple single primitive data items or arrays thereof and intended for data that will be constant over the course of an application’s execution. In applications using ADIOS2 as an IO framework, this will usually correspond with lightweight metadata.

Writing an attribute is atomic and does not allow for writing different positions within the attribute in a temporally or spatially distributed manner. The ADIOS2 framework will take care of collecting attributes written across different parallel processes (MPI ranks).

variables Compared to attributes, variables are more flexible in usage. Variables come in several kinds, the most common one being *global arrays*. Global

arrays are n -dimensional datasets of primitive data types. Their content may vary over time and writing may occur partially. Datasets may be written to in writing calls distributed temporally, i.e. one after another, as well as spatially, i.e. across parallel processes. The terminology *global* array refers to the latter point, as opposed to *local* arrays that are written by parallel processes independently. The same flexibility is available when reading from a dataset.

From the perspective of performance considerations, access patterns should be preferred during reading time that match the form that data has been written in. For correctness purposes, it is only necessary that regions be accessed that have actually been written, regardless of the physical chunks available in the backend.

Other more specialized forms of variables exist, ranging in flexibility of expression between the power of attributes and of global arrays. We do not use those special forms and refer to the official documentation for ADIOS2 for a more detailed explanation.

steps The consumption of data is organized in ADIOS2 by defining steps. By ending a step, a user can tell the ADIOS2 framework that all data pertaining to that step is now known to ADIOS2 and can hence be moved to storage. A dataset can hold different data across different steps, turning an n -dimensional dataset conceptually into an $(n + 1)$ -dimensional dataset. We will explain in chapter 3 why the ADIOS2 backend in the openPMD API does not make use of this capability. From the openPMD API’s perspective, the important aspect of steps lies in the possibility to describe units of data movement by using steps. Especially in streaming ADIOS2 engines, steps will correspond with single packets sent to and seen at once by readers.

The default engine since ADIOS2 in version 2.5 has been the BP4 engine (binary pack), taking succession of the older BP3 engine that maintains backwards compatibility with ADIOS1. Both of these engines store their data to disk and have seen creation during the development of the ADIOS framework in both versions. Alternatively, writing data in the format defined by the *hierarchical data format* in version 5 (HDF5) is optionally supported as a disk-based engine.

At the time of writing this Thesis, three engines are available for usage of ADIOS2 in streaming-based workflows. Most important for the purposes in this Master’s Thesis will be the *Sustainable Staging Support* (SST) engine that is intended “for use in HPC environments” and allows usage of RDMA networks, as well as communication via sockets in wide area networks (WAN). Compared to the other backends, it offers the largest flexibility by allowing for full $M \times N$ data distribution from writing to reading processes where M and N may be different numbers. Additionally,

distributing data to different reading codes at the same time is also possible using the SST engine.

The data distribution workflow is asynchronous, as is shown in figure 2.1. Data within one step is stored into buffers owned by the ADIOS2 framework in a marshalled format. In general, the data-producing application can continue computation after ending a step. Situations where ADIOS2 will block the producing application include firstly waiting for a reading application to register at the beginning of a simulation, as well as secondly the situation that the maximum number of buffered steps has been reached.

Upon ending a step as a producer, data consumers will see the step and its available data. A consumer will then communicate back to the producer what data it wants to load and finally load it upon either flushing or ending its reading step. This happens asynchronously to the continuing computation in the writing application.

Figure 2.1: Writing and reading a step in ADIOS2's SST engine

The other two streaming engines are firstly the InSituMPI engine, using the available implementation of the MPI standard on the system. It requires launching the application within the same MPI context and performs blocking IO, unlike the SST engine. Secondly, for staging within a wide area network the DataMan engine may be used.

A further special engine, at the time of writing without support in the openPMD API, is the Inline engine, allowing for communication within one process.

2.3 PIConGPU

A central algorithm used in computational plasma physics is the particle-in-cell (PIC) algorithm. Usage of this algorithm is adequate in plasma simulations whose dynamics cannot be properly modeled by ensemble averages such as in fluid approaches. Instead, this algorithm models the observed plasma by two means:

1. A so-called *mesh*, which is a discrete domain decomposition of the modeled plasma volume into single *cells*. This decomposition defines the granularity at which the electric field \vec{E} and the magnetic field \vec{B} are given.
2. Particle motion is described by defining (*macro-*) *particles* by charge q , mass m and a particle density distribution function around the macroparticle's position.

The name of the algorithm stems from the fact that it uses compute-heavy, but exact *particle* data at the same time as efficiently computable, but less exact *mesh* data. The dynamics of the observed plasma is then simulated by using an iterative 4-step approach based on Maxwell's equations.

One implementation of this algorithm is PIConGPU [5], developed at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf. It has been designed to make use of multi-GPU clusters, initially implemented using NVIDIA Cuda [29] and the message passing interface (MPI) [15]. A performance-portable implementation has since been devised using the Alpaka accelerator abstraction library [40, 41], allowing for execution on non-NVIDIA GPU hardware as well as on CPU-only systems.

Since its creation, PIConGPU has seen a growing plugin infrastructure a part of which can be seen in figure 2.2 on the next page. The plugins are in general tightly coupled with PIConGPU and not usable as freestanding applications. Next to analysis and visualization plugins working on the data produced by PIConGPU, two raw IO plugins are provided with ADIOS and HDF5. These communicate directly with the IO libraries of the same name, producing usually massive amounts of raw data, usable for either restarting from a checkpoint or as input for further separately executed applications.

As described above, the PIC algorithm will work on particle-mesh data. Naturally, its data dumps take this format as well. Both the ADIOS and HDF5 plugins format their output manually according to the openPMD standard, but without making use of the openPMD API which at the time of implementing these plugins was not sufficiently stable yet.

Figure 2.2: Subset of the PIConGPU plugin infrastructure

For its internal computations, however, PIConGPU does not use a data layout that conforms with the openPMD standard. As an example, PIConGPU will internally not use three separate buffers for describing the x , y and z positions of particles, but instead one large buffer that will contain every single particle’s information in a contiguous chunk of memory. The IO plugins will hence put the data to be written through several stages of preparation before finally writing to disk: After copying data from device memory to host memory, it has to be rearranged to conform with the openPMD standard. Next, preparations within the IO plugin, such as e.g. marshalling, will ensue. After this step, the IO backend can write to persistent memory.

2.4 GAPD

GAPD is an “atom-based polychromatic diffraction simulation code for direct, kinematics-based simulations of X-ray/electron diffraction of large-scale atomic systems with mono-/polychromatic beams and arbitrary plane detector geometries” [13]. As such, it falls into the category of typical analysis codes that may be run on the raw data produced by a simulation such as PIConGPU. It will take into regard only particle data while ignoring mesh data produced by PIConGPU or similar simulations.

Preceding implementations of the same analysis include SLADS by Chen and E [8] which scales to multiple compute nodes via the use of the message passing interface, as well as the Python library PyNX by Favre-Nicolin et al. [14] that is GPU-accelerated, but cannot scale to several GPU nodes. By implementing GAPD to make use of GPU clusters, E et al. [13] are able to simulate diffraction patterns of systems up to ~ 5 billion atoms. With the initial implementation done in terms of the NVIDIA Cuda [29] library, performance portability has been achieved by using the Cupla and Alpaka abstraction libraries [37, 41], making use of GPU as well as CPU hardware as available.

Performing this analysis is not only interesting from the perspective of extracting meaningful and interpretable data from the massive amounts of raw data that the simulation manipulates, it is also valuable as a means of reducing the amount of data to be processed via IO systems by several orders of magnitude down from the number of raw macroparticles to the number of points in reciprocal space. E et al. [13] mention numbers of 10^8 raw atoms and 10^5 points in reciprocal space as still being a time-consuming challenge to the CPU-based parallel code SLADS.

The potential for reducing IO load by using such an analysis is before the beginning of this Master's Thesis not usable from GAPD. While GAPD implements numerous IO routines to read from different formats, all these routines read data from the file system in text format. No routine is available for reading from binary-based formats nor from streams. Implementing such capabilities is part of this Master's Thesis.

Chapter 3

Particle-Mesh Data in a Streaming Workflow

This chapter is dedicated to the creation of a streaming framework building upon the openPMD API and ADIOS2. We will begin with a discussion on tight and loose coupling, their differences, advantages and disadvantages. We continue by shortly laying out objectives for the envisioned streaming framework and the role that ADIOS2 and the openPMD API play in the creation of a streaming-enabled plasma-physical simulation workflow. The remainder of this chapter concerns itself with the steps taken to build this framework.

3.1 Tight coupling versus loose coupling

Typically, physical simulations consist logically not only of a single simulation, but of several codes that are coupled in a simulation pipeline. Next to the actual simulation, the produced data might be processed in several stages of analysis, visualization and data accumulation. Next to acyclic simulation pipelines, feedback simulations are also thinkable where two or more applications exchange data in a bidirectional manner. A tightly-coupled example for such a workflow has been examined by Dominski et al. [12] and Klasky et al. [24] between the core-continuum code GENE and the particle-in-cell code XGC.

The terms “*tight coupling*” and “*loose coupling*” define how this logical pipeline and the interaction between single logical stages are implemented in concrete. Two perspectives can be taken to regard tight versus loose coupling:

workflow From the perspective of application development and execution workflow, loose coupling implies that the single stages of a simulation pipeline are

developed, built and executed in separate. Tightly coupled simulations, however, are developed as one application that is then compiled to and launched as one program.

physical Physically, tightly coupled codes correspond with being single processes in the operating system and sharing virtual address rooms between the logical components of the coupled simulation. Attention must be paid not to confuse this concept with parallelization of one application across several processes, e.g. for applications developed in terms of the message passing interface.

Loosely coupled applications cannot communicate by sharing addresses and must rely on other methods to do so. Investigating such alternative ways shall be a defining topic of this Thesis.

A loosely coupled application comes hence with greater flexibility. As long as applications within a domain can agree on a communication standard, a single component in the simulation pipeline is not restricted to usage in its designated position, but can be used freestanding or in other simulations setups as required by the situation. This greatly reduces developmental overhead as well as complexity of otherwise monolithic simulation frameworks.

The increased flexibility is not restricted to the simulation setups, but also applies to mapping the processes to fitting hardware components. If for example one stage of the simulation pipeline is best run on GPU hardware accelerators, but another stage is predestined for conventional CPU hardware, the fact that components in a loosely coupled simulation pipeline are executed independently makes it easy to run each application as is best suitable for its needs. In tight coupling, this is only possible if explicitly programmed into the application, often resulting in mixing hardware description with simulation code. In times of hardware becoming increasingly heterogeneous, as is shown by the continuing march-through by GPU hardware and the onsetting spreading of FPGA hardware in the TOP500 list [28], upholding flexibility through loose coupling shows to be valuable.

This increased flexibility comes at the cost of less efficient communication. In tight coupling, one stage of the simulation can ideally directly access data written by a previous stage. In loose coupling, however, data movement becomes necessary as a measure to fetch data into the own virtual address space. We note, that in our previous example that mentioned the ability to execute single stages on different compute partitions, data movement across partitions will additionally become necessary from the hardware's perspective.

Due to the valuable flexibility obtainable through loose coupling, such workflows are oftentimes already the norm in many domains, including plasma physical simulations, accepting performance losses due to inefficient communication. We find freestanding visualization tools [9, 26] as well as freestanding analysis tools [13, 34,

8]. By this design choice, they have greater flexibility over comparable tools tightly integrated with a simulation framework such as PIconGPU [5] at the cost of IO performance getting relevance. With computation performance continuing to develop faster than performance of memory and file system accesses – especially in times of increased usage of hardware accelerators – the drawbacks in these workflows become increasingly apparent. Such simulation pipelines still often rely on sharing data between the single stages via persistent file systems, simply because this approach is convenient and has traditionally worked well enough.

Figure 3.1

Nowadays however, the limits of parallel file systems are often reached by large-scale simulations. Once the maximum parallel bandwidth of the file system is in use, no further scaling of the application through parallelization is feasible as long as this bottleneck persists. While successful attempts have been made at pushing these boundaries further, e.g. through utilization of unused compute resources by compression [21], the observed issue calls for a more fundamental change in workflows in order to avoid accessing persistent storage if not needed. To this end, we make use of the fact that current workflows are set up as heterogeneous loosely-coupled simulation pipelines in the way previously described. In a simulation setup as shown in the first subfigure of figure 3.1, the analyzed data is often several orders of magnitude smaller, but contains at the same time the actual data of interest while the raw data produced by the initial simulation is not used as a final result. For this reason, the usage of persistent storage is at the same time not required for the raw data as well as not technically feasible due to the sheer amount of data.

3.2 Objectives and Approach

While the performance of tight coupling – that under ideal circumstances works without copying data – is out of reach for loose coupling, we intend hence to enable workflows of physical simulation pipelines that bypass persistent storage and use high-speed network infrastructures available on modern cluster systems for communication between the single simulation stages – as seen in the righthand side of figure 3.1. Such a workflow can only succeed in creating the described form of flexibility in coupling codes as needed if agreement on a common standard for communication between codes is found. We use the emerging openPMD standard and API that provides a domain-specific data description and extend it with streaming capabilities.

Piacentini et al. [30] argue that one central motivation for coupling is to reuse legacy codes. In accordance with this notion, we intend to enable streaming workflows without requiring the user to change too much code coming from file-based IO procedures. The openPMD API and ADIOS2 lend themselves to create such facilities since both libraries put emphasis on separating data description from storage backends (named *engines* in ADIOS2 and *backends* in the openPMD API).

ADIOS2 provides several engines for streaming, but is laid out for generic data from any domain. For this reason, describing particle-mesh data using bare ADIOS2 is – while possible – error-prone. The openPMD API on the other hand allows for a straightforward description of particle-mesh data according to the openPMD standard, but its design originally targets file-based IO backends.

A number of physical codes that read and/or produce particle-mesh data already use the openPMD API for file-based IO [26, 9, 31, 34]. The objective is to allow easily transforming such file-based procedures to streaming-based ones without changing the description of data.

With file-based IO methods, the openPMD API allows changing backends by switching the file name’s extension. By the very nature of streaming, it will not be possible in general to transform a file-based to a streaming-based IO procedure using openPMD by applying only such minuscule changes. The semantics of data movement become increasingly relevant in a streaming workflow, hence adaptations in the writing as well the reading code will be necessary. As a stated objective, those adaptations shall remain independent of the description of particle-mesh data in the problem domain.

3.3 Streaming concepts in the openPMD API

We describe the adaptations seen in the openPMD API that have been put in place to enable a streaming workflow as well as how these adaptations relate to the

concrete streaming implementation in terms of the ADIOS2 framework.

3.3.1 The flush-advance cycle

So far, the openPMD API has one central method `Series::flush` used to guarantee data movement to the chosen backend. It guarantees that all previously enqueued actions will be performed. This has effects at two sites:

- *In the running program:* Flushing a Series guarantees that all user buffers are written or read and can be reused.
- *In the backend:* Flushing a Series guarantees data movement to/from the backend.

In order to provide for a more fine-grained control over data movement, we separate both notions:

flush Flush is restricted to the application-side guarantees. After flushing a Series, all buffers will be reusable, but data needs not necessarily be available in the backend.

advance Advancing a Series guarantees that backends are synchronized with the performed operations (in writing mode) or with the operations to be performed (in reading mode). In writing mode, this implies that written data will have moved to the storage after finishing this call. In reading mode however, this ensures data availability in the storage. This latter point is crucial in streaming contexts, but may also allow disk-based openPMD backends to implement certain optimizations such as pre-fetching data.

Figure 3.2: Lifecycle of a streamed data packet, from writing simulation to reading analysis

We describe further the effects and nuances of advancing a Series, in writing as well as in reading mode. For a visualization, follow figure 3.2 on the previous page.

- *When writing:* In order to guarantee data movement of all operations that have been enqueued previously, it is necessary also to flush the Series upon advancing. In streaming mode, this demarks the end of one sent streaming packet.
- *When reading:* While advancing a Series in writing mode is also useful in file-based mode, doing so in reading mode is mostly relevant within the boundaries of a streaming workflow. In a streaming workflow, the backend needs not hold the data of the current packet available anymore, so this is the last chance to flush any previous operations. In order not to perform operations on data that is not available any longer, all operations enqueued prior to this `advance` call are flushed. All successive flushes will work on the new data.

It depends on the concrete implementation in a backend where data lives between `flush` and `advance`. By the above definitions, we have two guarantees: Firstly, data *cannot* occupy user buffers after flushing in write mode or before flushing in read mode – and secondly, data *must* occupy the backend’s storage after advancing in write mode or before advancing in read mode. This leaves little options for the intermediate storage: Either there exists a tertiary storage next to user buffers and the final storage or data is passed through directly to/from the final storage upon flushing.

Some backends will actually make use of such a tertiary storage. This includes the *Sustainable Staging Transport* engine in ADIOS2 where data is marshalled upon being seen by the backend into an ADIOS2-owned buffer and written to transport upon advancing. However, the predominant reason to include a flush-advance cycle in the data movement description of the openPMD API is to provide flexibility in the choice of data packets that are written to storage or transport and to provide for a generic description of data movement that will be possible to implement in upcoming streaming backends as well. Setting backend-targeting storage granularities via *advance* independently from *flushing* user-side buffers allows firstly easy adaptation of codes that are written with disk-based storage in mind without requiring to manipulate the simulation’s memory management – and secondly, migration of codes that are already streaming-aware to platforms with stricter or looser memory requirements is possible with similar ease since granularity of sent packets can be quickly adapted to changing requirements. Depending on the concrete backend, this can potentially go at the expense of performance through usage of intermediate data structures, so on the writer’s side, workflows should be preferred where all data for one streaming packet is presented at once such that flushing becomes unnecessary. Similarly, it is advisable to load all data of one packet on the reader’s end within one

single flush. Concerning the ADIOS2 backend, this is actually the more important requirement, since putting data into intermediate structures on the writer's end is required due to marshalling anyway, but on the reader's end communication back to the writer can be minimized by bundling it up into one call.

3.3.2 Relation of the Flush-Advance-Cycle to ADIOS2 steps

The method of choice for implementing streaming workflows in ADIOS2 is the so-called *step*. Instead of only one method `advance` to mark the line between two packets as in the openPMD API, ADIOS2 steps are described using two methods: `BeginStep` and `EndStep`. As opposed to the low-level API ADIOS2, in openPMD we decide for a more implicit handling of streaming steps/packets with only one API call.

A user might also wish to have a more fine-grained control over the steps. Especially in reading mode, dropping the current packet and receiving the next packet are two events that both form part of advancing a Series, but might be temporally far apart from each other. We solve this by using the `future` API in C++. The current packet will be dropped as soon as the Series is advanced, but availability of subsequent data is only guaranteed once the `future` has a result. This result is a status code that can be used to inspect whether a next packet has been successfully awaited, the stream is over or an error has occurred.

If fine-grained control is required, the future object can hence be used to provide for it. Otherwise, the user can choose not to bind the returned future to a value which will cause the future to be immediately awaited through object destruction.

The streaming API is at the time of writing not yet integrated into the Python interface of the openPMD API where another design will be necessary due to the garbage-collected nature of the language that does not guarantee deterministic object destruction.

More importantly, ADIOS2 steps bear at the same time a semantical and a physical meaning. Next to defining the packets of a streaming-based workflow, ADIOS2 steps may also be used to define several versions of the same data. The same dataset may be written to several times across several steps and all versions of this dataset will be maintained by ADIOS2. The motivation behind this design is the same as behind openPMD's *iterations*. We do not leverage this to the openPMD API for two reasons:

- Using ADIOS steps to represent iterations is not compatible with the data layout of the openPMD standard. The openPMD standard defines iterations as separate groups with hierarchy trees independent from one another. A semantically equivalent dataset in two different iterations will be modeled as two physically distinct and independent datasets. With ADIOS steps however, a

layout would be required where both iterations would be modeled as two versions of the same dataset. Instead of n separate trees for each iteration, there would be one tree. This is a much stricter layout that requires to modify previously defined data layouts – such as dataset extents, datatypes or attribute values – as soon as it opposes definitions made in previous iterations.

- While ADIOS2 is a generic IO framework, openPMD is domain specific and clearly prescribes how to structure data into iterations. Attention must be paid to allow users to select packet sizes as freely as possible. Coupling the very strictly prescribed semantical meaning of iterations in the domain of particle-mesh data with the physical meaning in the domain of data movement is hence unsatisfactory since it leaves users without a way to select the size of data packets, given a Series that is intended to be written. By separating iterations from the division of data into packets, we allow the user to send a complete iteration at once, only parts of a complete iteration at once or even several iterations at the same time, possibly allowing for a more adequate resource usage.

Sending data as seldom as possible should hereby be preferred from the IO system’s perspective in order to minimize single IO actions and in order to favor few large operations over many small ones. Since data has to be staged on the writer’s node until sending, this goes along the requirements by available memory. Greater opportunity to pipeline parallel processing should be taken into regard as a reason to send packets not too seldom. Allowing to make design choices between these opposing goals requires leaving this leeway up to the user of the openPMD API.

Figure 3.3: Data subdivisions physically and semantically

3.3.3 Logical layers in the openPMD API

In summary, the description of data and data movement is split into steps on two independent levels, as shown in figure 3.3 on the facing page.

semantically Through openPMD’s iterations that may be written in any order. This corresponds with the legacy backend-independent iteration layout in the openPMD standard and API.

physically Through advance steps with intermittent flushes. The implementation is backend-dependent.

Figure 3.4: Layers of data description in the openPMD API

We obtain a separation of the description of particle-mesh data in three layers, as shown in figure 3.4 and further detailed in the following:

- *Particle-mesh semantic in the frontend:* This is intentionally largely unchanged from file-based openPMD since data description in the problem domain shall remain independent from description of data movement. This layer allows defining the structure of openPMD standard-conforming datasets in an idiomatic C++/Python API.
- *Semantics of data movement in the frontend:* The openPMD API presents a unified view on data movement, independent from the chosen backend. To enforce this, the user does not include backend-specific headers and describes data movement only by openPMD methods available across backends. This layer has seen a number of changes.

As described previously, this layer has been extended with streaming-friendly semantics through definition of the flush-advance-cycle.

Previously, the openPMD API only allowed to set backend-specific configuration options via environment variables. Since setting backend-specific options becomes increasingly relevant in streaming-based workflows, we seek to provide for a more manageable method, at the same time without requiring to write backend-specific code. We solve this by allowing to set configuration options formatted in JSON and interpreted by the backends. We will go into further detail in the following.

- *Concrete implementation of such a workflow in the backends:* Part of this Thesis is the implementation of the ADIOS2 backend in openPMD. While the streaming semantics of the openPMD API can be implemented in a straightforward manner in terms of ADIOS2, we designed the streaming semantics in a way that keeps the openPMD extensible to further streaming-based backends, including e.g. blocking IO.

3.3.4 Backend-specific configuration

Part of this division of data description into the three layers is that user code will not include backend-specific code. This way, maximum flexibility can be achieved, not tying the data description in a simulation code to a specific backend. A challenge in this approach is the configuration of backends. For ADIOS2, the backend that has seen creation over the course of this Master’s Thesis, important parameters include the engine that ADIOS2 will use – this choice implies whether a streaming or disk-based workflow will be used – and their respective configurations, such as buffer allocation strategies or the choice between sockets and RDMA (remote direct memory access) for streaming. While configuration of backends is not streaming-related in particular, the necessity to explicitly configure the chosen openPMD backend arises very dominantly in this context. We take the chance to replace the legacy solution for this issue via environment variables through a description that is hopefully more structured, descriptive and reliable. Given that the openPMD API already ships with a JSON backend, we choose to use a JSON-formatted string for configuring backend parameters.

JSON gives us the chance to pass backend-specific parameters in an explicit way within a well-defined expressive structure, while at the same time providing us with a format that is backend-agnostic. Validity of the parameter string is then checked at runtime and processed as defined by the concrete backend. A simple configuration object is found in the following. We note, that one single openPMD configuration JSON object can hold configurations for several openPMD backends at the same time, allowing users to keep one configuration while switching between backends. The concrete formatting of a backend’s configuration and its interpretation is dictated by that backend.

```
{
  "backend": "adios2",
  "adios2": {
    "engine": {
      "type": "sst",
      "parameters": {
        "BufferGrowthFactor": "2.0",
```

```

        "DataTransport": "RDMA",
        "QueueLimit": "2"
    }
},
" hdf5": {
    ["add", "hdf5", "configuration", "here"]
}
}

```

3.3.5 Explicitly finalizing iterations

We add to the frontend of the openPMD API functionality to declare an iteration finalized. This serves a number of purposes. Firstly, in streaming mode this is the only way for a reader to know that all relevant data for an iteration has been sent. For the reading instance of the openPMD API, this means that this iteration does not have to be parsed for changes. The application then knows that all information on this iteration is complete and can be used as such in subsequent calculations.

This functionality lends itself to implement further optimizations, relying on the knowledge that an iteration is not going to change. For one, the openPMD API does currently not provide a mechanism to close a file before the end of a simulation. For disk-based workflows, the openPMD API provides a so-called “file-based” layout where each iteration will be written to a separate “file” – which might also be a folder depending on the chosen backend. It is in general preferable to close an iteration’s file as early as possible. Especially in simulations with a large number of parallel processes as well as a large number of iterations, this would otherwise result in numbers of file descriptors that easily exceed the allowable number in common Linux systems. On the other hand, in case of crashes it is good to have written data cleanly closed to guarantee usability of intermediate results and checkpoint data. In this file-based layout, we hence pass through a hint to backend that an iteration’s file can be closed upon finalizing it.

3.4 Implementation challenges

We describe challenges relating to the handling of metadata that arose during the implementation of the streaming API. The first challenge relates to streaming in a backend-independent manner, the second one relates to the interaction of the openPMD standard and API with ADIOS2.

3.4.1 Parsing an openPMD Series

A simulation’s data layout needs not be defined up front in the openPMD API. While each data packet is required to be a fully-defined openPMD standard conforming dataset, this dataset may – and will in general – be a subset of the complete dataset to come. Within disk-based workflows, the complete dataset is known upon opening a file. In a streaming workflow however, this means that the Series must be constantly monitored for changes.

The parsing process is triggered by *advancing* a Series in read mode. Since the openPMD structure is exposed to user code through handles that point to internal representations, we make sure not to invalidate previously created handles in the parsing process. This way, the parsing process becomes largely transparent to the user code.

More importantly, a naïve implementation will multiply the asymptotic runtime of the parsing overhead with the number of times that the Series is advanced. We avoid such an overhead by parsing anew only iterations that have not yet been declared finalized. This way, we make use of an information that is already available in the API, not requiring more pervasive changes. This is sufficient, since the parsing process is not the bottleneck of the coupled communication. Rather do we intend to allow scaling simulations to a large number of iterations. Since with this change, parsing is restricted to fixed-sized windows of the complete openPMD structure, this goal is achieved and the time spent for parsing does not grow linear with the size of the dataset unlike in the trivial solution.

3.4.2 Dealing with large numbers of attributes

In streaming-based workflows, the data layout as defined by the openPMD standard causes a performance issue noticeable in simulations amassing large numbers of iterations. The standard mandates that an iteration is a group in the openPMD hierarchy, including all information about this iteration’s physical data in a self-contained manner. This contradicts the preferred layout in ADIOS2 where attributes are step-ignorant and each variable (i.e. multidimensional dataset) is available in every ADIOS step. In disk-based ADIOS engines, the steps are conceptually stored as an additional dimension of each variable. See subsection 3.3.2 for further details. Contradicting this approach, the physical meta information has to be newly set up and defined for each iteration in the openPMD standard, with usually a three-digit number of attributes per iteration (136 attributes per iteration for the Laser Wakefield example simulation [32]). Our choice to avoid the data layout preferred by ADIOS2, results in a great number of attributes that we have to handle.

As mentioned in subsection 3.3.3, we do not modify the data layout as defined by the openPMD standard. A solution has hence to be found within the boundaries

of the backend’s implementation. The issue is of lesser relevance in disk-based workflows since the openPMD standard and API allow storing iterations as separate “files”. For a given simulation, the meta data structure for one iteration is usually fixed in size and does not scale with the number of iterations. The term “file” has to be interpreted in the context of the chosen backend and can in reality also correspond with a folder on disk, e.g. in the case of ADIOS2’s BP4 engine. This solution is not applicable in a sensible way in a streaming workflow, since it would correspond with opening and closing a stream for each iteration anew. The overhead from this for the operating system as well as the application is not acceptable. Additionally, such a workaround would sabotage optimizations that ADIOS2 can provide if one engine is kept open. An example is the reuse of data buffers across ADIOS2 steps in the SST engine that will be included as an optimization once the serialization engine of SST has been ported to make use of BP4 serialization.

We approach the problem from openPMD’s side by reducing the number of attributes being sent and read. This is made possible by use of an optimization allowing for an implementation that does not affect the openPMD standard, but only applying for streaming mode. This is an acceptable compromise, since in disk mode the issue can be largely avoided by choosing the aforementioned file-based layout. After declaring an iteration finalized, the backend will receive a hint that the corresponding group in the hierarchy is now “stale”. For the backend – in our case ADIOS2 – this means that the group needs not be kept in a parseable state from now on, i.e. attributes and variables contained in this group may now be deleted. In disk-based mode however, it must be guaranteed that parsing attempts that correspond with an earlier step will successfully see those attributes. openPMD backends may also choose to use this hint for optimizations in disk-based layouts, for simplicity reasons we currently restrict this optimization to streaming mode in the ADIOS2 backend. This way, a constant number of attributes is achieved instead of linear growth with the number of iterations.

An efficient implementation of inquiring available attributes is also necessary. It must be avoided that the runtime costs of single operations on ADIOS2 variables or attributes scale with the size of the dataset. In disk-based workflows, this was previously avoided by using openPMD’s file-based iteration formatting where every iteration is written as a separate file. This comes with the advantage that only fixed-sized units – one iteration – needed to be parsed at once. We argued previously that this is not feasible in a streaming workflow, so implementing the parsing procedure to scale well with large datasets becomes imperative.

Since a group-based iteration layout, i.e. all data will be written to one dataset, is also eligible when using disk-based backends, both streaming and disk-based workflows will profit from taking care of making the parsing procedure well-scalable. We test a first naïve implementation with a dataset containing thirty iterations as

produced by the Laser Wakefield simulation in PIconGPU. The dataset written with the BP4 engine contains 682 variables and 4247 attributes. Opening it in the openPMD API takes around 20 seconds which shows an unacceptable scaling behavior.

The major time sink in this measurement can be traced back to looking up available attributes and variables. Firstly, such lookups, if done directly within the ADIOS2 framework, are always linear in the number of attributes/variables that are found. We solve this by buffering the returned values within the openPMD API. Secondly, since the openPMD standard mandates a hierarchical layout, such lookups usually come in the form of a prefix-based lookup. Given for example an openPMD group of the form `/data/1000/E`, only attributes and variables beginning with exactly that prefix must be taken into consideration when reading the contents of this group. We make use of the fact that ADIOS2 organizes the known attributes and variables in the C++ standard template library's `std::map` class whose string-indexed instance is sorted lexicographically, allowing for efficient prefix-based lookups.

By implementing both of these improvements, the parsing time for the above dataset is reduced to half a second.

Chapter 4

Implementing a streaming workflow

A framework for the description of a streaming-enabled workflow using particle-mesh data according to the openPMD standard has been described in the previous chapter. In this chapter, we will focus on the concrete implementation of such a workflow in a coupled simulation that uses PIconGPU [5] as data source and GAPD [13] as data sink. Several questions arise whose answers bear stronger implications than in a file-based setup. We observe and explain a two-dimensional distribution of data along time – i.e. single streaming steps – and along space – i.e. single instances of a parallel application distributed across parallel hardware. We will first describe the implications of this distribution application-independently and show strategies and patterns to approach the organization of data in a streaming workflow. Having discussed the different options and strategies, we will then explain what choices needed to be made for an implementation in our example setup and what implications these decisions had on the single codes.

4.1 Data distribution along time

When writing particle-mesh data to persistent storage, there are (almost) no dependencies between applications concerning the patterns in which data is produced and consumed. The reading code will only be invoked once the writing code has finished writing and will random-access data in the way that fits its own requirements best. While access along the written chunks is to be preferred for IO efficiency reasons, it is not necessary from a correctness perspective.

The situation can be considered comparable to the situation found in pipelining on UNIX-like shells [3]. There, we can find tools such as the stream-editor `sed` or `grep` that work on single chunks of input data in a naturally streaming fashion,

making it possible to avoid buffering input data by chaining commands in a pipeline. On the other hand, there are tools such as `tac` which is used to print an input file/stream in reverse. By the very nature of this problem, the complete input will need to be buffered before any output can be written.

Similar to this, applications are well-suited as sink codes if they support pipeline parallelism inasmuch as data can be processed in that order that it arrives in.

This comparison hides a further level of complexity that arises when streaming particle-mesh data. Other than UNIX pipelining where data is communicated in form of linear byte streams, two different codes that produce openPMD data may write this data in completely different logical forms.

The reading application can hence not expect a canonical format for the distribution of data along time, but will instead need a strategy to deal with the patterns of data arrival. We will first discuss a trivial, but still useful strategy to achieve this and afterwards go into detail about some special patterns and their effects on a reading application.

Accumulate data on the reader's end A first easy approach is to simply accumulate data on the reader's end until all data is available that the code would also use in a filesystem-based workflow. Such an accumulation is only scalable on a per-iteration level, allowing to use a constant amount of memory. While not leveraging all benefits of a streaming workflow, this approach is still useful in a number of occasions:

1. The reading code that is being used in a streaming pipeline of openPMD data does not provide for an easy adaptation to pipelining support.
2. Such an adaptation would be possible, but too time-intensive to implement.
3. The reading code should be able to consume data from various applications that produce their data in different logical orders.
4. The used hardware provides for sufficient memory to enable accumulation.

This approach will necessarily carry over some of the downsides of a filesystem-based workflow. For one, the sequentialization of codes as known in such workflows persists since the sink needs to wait until the source has finished writing a consumable amount of data. Despite this, a more coarse-grained level of pipeline parallelism can still be exploited at a per-iteration level. Also, the sink application is now responsible for buffering the data which had previously been buffered in persistent storage.

Despite these downsides, this approach is still viable since it enjoys one of the central benefits of streaming: avoiding the file system. Even though the memory

overhead persists, such a simulation can be expected to scale better to large numbers of compute units since the filesystem bottleneck is avoided and a coarse-grained level of pipeline parallelism is present.

For usability and ease of coupling codes, this approach maintains the valuable property of filesystem-based workflows that the sink code does not depend heavily on the organization of data into packets by the writing code.

Hence, this approach is to be preferred if one is interested in avoiding the filesystem's bottlenecks, but not interested in heavily adapting the involved codes. If, however, accumulation is to be avoided, data must be consumed in accordance with the pattern that the data source produces. This leads to the other side of accumulation.

Sending a complete iteration at once The equivalent on the writer's end of accumulating data is to send complete iterations at once, i.e. accumulate data before sending. Just like accumulating data on the reader's end, this is only feasible as long as sufficient memory is available to hold the data before sending.

Similar to how accumulation on the reader end makes it easy to read data from several different data sources, accumulation on the writer end will enable a greater number of data sinks to read from the writer.

An additional positive effect can be seen insofar as IO in general prefers few large operations over the overhead incurring by performing many small operations. Sending more data in one packet will hence reduce the amount of communication necessary between readers and writers – at the cost of requiring to hold data either in the writer's or the reader's application memory depending on the implementing backend.

In a high-level view, accumulating data either on the writer's or the reader's end will perform exactly that form of buffering intermediate results that is traditionally implemented via filesystem IO, yielding better chances for code reuse.

Moving on from accumulation, we observe a number of typical patterns in the way that data may be commonly produced in and their effects on reading codes.

Streaming a complete physical region in a packet Applications' legacy IO methods may be designed to output data by physical region in the observed n -dimensional space. When extending such methods for streaming support, the straightforward implementation is sending one complete region as a single packet. Receiving applications will benefit from this layout if their computed problem is easily parallelizable by splitting the domain into chunks. The receiving code can then operate on one single region independently since it knows all potentially available physical quantities in that space. Global operations such as computing blurs will likely require accumulating data before they can be performed

Streaming a complete species in a packet Other applications' IO methods, such as the writing code at hand in this Master's Thesis – PIconGPU, are designed to output a complete species / field type globally at once. The most straightforward implementation of streaming in this case is to send and consume a complete field / species at once. A reading code will be able to compute global operations in this mode, but only one field type / species type will be available at a time. One single packet does not contain complete information about any part of the space. Codes that are used to compute interactions between different types of species will hence be forced to accumulate several steps worth of data before starting.

Subslicing datasets If datasets get large, they may as well be sent in several packets one after another. Attention should be paid to the fact that one logical dataset (such as the particles of one species in an iteration) is split into several physically independent datasets by the openPMD standard (such as the particle's x , y and z positions).

The openPMD API will hence allow codes to send data in sub-packets such that one packet contains only partial information on a single particle, but a second code might not be able to process such a stream. See figure 4.1 for a visualization. If feasible in the writing code, the same sub-chunking should be applied to those datasets to help a reading code process those chunks more easily.

Figure 4.1

Make use of backend-specific features in ADIOS2? As explained in chapter 3, the ADIOS2 library supports writing to the same position of datasets several times in different steps. This sees support for file engines as well as for streaming engines. We have previously explained why this facility is not used to model iterations in the openPMD API.

If an application is written from the beginning with streaming in mind, this feature may be used to stream particle data. If the writing application sends an equivalent number of particles in each packet, both involved applications will not need to write to / read from different positions in each packet. This is less useful for mesh data since the index is actually semantically valuable in the physical domain, so reusing an index does not make sense.

If the code is also intended to support writing to disk, this approach should be adopted carefully since backend-dependent behavior will be provoked in the openPMD API:

- Backends may overwrite data, thus losing information. Similarly, backends may refuse to overwrite data, also losing information.
- Backends (such as ADIOS2) may remember all versions, thus not losing data but creating datasets that do not conform with the openPMD standard.

For compatibility reasons with the openPMD standard and portability across different backends in the openPMD API, we will only use ADIOS2 steps to split written data into streaming chunks and not use this feature's ability to model different versions of datasets.

4.2 Data distribution along space

In disk-based workflows, the complete dataset is usually available in persistent storage and a reading code concerns itself mostly with the question of what data it wants to load. In a streaming workflow however, a second question arises: What data is available? In order to load data correctly and efficiently, both of these questions must be taken into account.

So far, the openPMD API does not concern itself with the question of data availability, hence adequate extensions must be made. We follow two separate approaches: Firstly, we extend the existing random-access based workflow such that it observes data availability. This is useful for leveraging file-based implementations of loose coupling that have been built upon the concept of random access. Secondly, we implement a workflow that allows greater flexibility in the choice of distribution strategies for chunks and subchunks, while taking control from the reading code what data exactly is loaded. This naturally requires that a reading code can deal with the introduced vagueness. If the data sink allows for this, adapting the data flow to the hardware at hand is possible with minimal changes to the code. We will make use of this flexibility later to benchmark different data distribution strategies.

The question of data availability is not solely of importance for streaming workflows. Also in disk-based storages, a single dataset may be decomposed into several

physical chunks. The IO performance of an analysis code that reads data from persistent storage will hence benefit from taking into account this physical structure.

Regardless of the strategy being used, we allow inquiring the available blocks of data in the openPMD API. While the openPMD standard already allows describing this as part of the dataset using the so-called `particlePatches`, this functionality is not restricted to particle datasets but may apply to any dataset. Its implementation however depends on the backend in use and is hence less generic than the `particlePatches`.

Random-access based approach Coming from a file-based implementation of loose coupling, data will in general be loaded into a reading code, using the method `RecordComponent::loadChunk`. This method allows the user to explicitly select a chunk of data for a given dataset (represented by a `RecordComponent` object) and load it into a chunk of memory.

Figure 4.2: Loading chunks – available chunks versus inquired chunk. The inquired chunk within the complete dataset is shown in blue, the available chunks in yellow. Only the intersecting regions will be loaded.

In a streaming context, attention must be paid to not accidentally load a chunk of data that is not present yet. We hence add an alternative method `loadAvailableChunksContiguous` that loads all data that is available within one given chunk. This way, the selected chunk might contain a number of smaller chunks that are actually available, as shown in figure 4.2. Any of these chunks need not necessarily represent a contiguous slice of memory to be written to. Since ADIOS does at the time of writing this not yet support loading data non-contiguously in the described way, this method will write each loaded sub-chunk to a contiguous chunk of memory. Helper functionality is provided to reorganize these chunks into the destination dataset.

	explicit selection user selects chunks	algorithmic distribution API assigns chunks
advantages	necessary if data distribution requires domain-specific knowledge	more resource-efficient, strategies can be changed flexibly
drawbacks	$n \times m$ communication patterns in the worst-case	difficult to encode domain-specific requirements

Algorithmic chunk distribution We implement algorithmic chunk distribution in a two-phase approach. The first phase will use meta-information about reading and writing ranks, e.g. hostnames, and create a partial assignment of chunks to be loaded by the reading ranks. Chunk distribution based on rank meta-information might make assumptions about the running processes which under suboptimal circumstances need not be fulfilled. An example is the cooperation of running processes within one compute node: If the simulations are executing such that there exists a node occupied completely by the source simulation, no sink rank will be assigned to process the chunks produced on that node. Hence, the first pass has a heuristical nature, yielding in general a partial result.

For this reason, we add a second phase to the algorithm that does in general not use the aforementioned meta-information and concerns itself solely with assigning the leftover chunks, turning a partial assignment into a full one. The full abstract procedure is seen in figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Two-phase based chunk mapping

Required knowledge needed as input for the algorithms consists of the available chunks to load as well as meta-information about the writing and reading processes.

The workflow of the chunk mapping algorithm within the cooperative procedure between source and sink is sketched in figure 4.4 on the following page. In this workflow, we use the openPMD standard’s ability to carry user-defined attributes for the

meta-information on running processes, which we make the preferred way to let the writing application tell the reading application about its own computational circumstances. Each application is responsible for calculating its own meta-information, the writer then attaches its information as an attribute to the openPMD structure. Knowing about available chunks is the concrete backend’s task.

Since only the reader knows about its own application-specific requirements while the writer does not even necessarily know which readers are going to be active, it is the reader’s responsibility to select chunks to load and announce them back to the writer. Because of this, the reader will now inspect the meta-data sent by the reader and applies the algorithm sketched in figure 4.3. The automated chunk selection algorithms described in the following will hence be executed on the sink side. The calculated chunks are announced back to the writer within the scope of the concrete backend. Actual heavy-weight data can now be loaded.

Figure 4.4: Calculation of chunks within the workflow of a coupled simulation

For the first phase, we use a simple implementation that assigns chunks to reading processes such that communication only happens within one compute node. In the following, we will assume that the meta-information will be hostnames, but this is not necessary. The described algorithm will more precisely ensure that chunks are assigned in such a way, that the reading rank will have the same meta-information (given as a string) as the respective chunk’s writing rank. This way, also subdivisions that are more fine-grained or more coarse-grained than single compute nodes are

implementable using this algorithm.

Algorithm 1 Implementation of the first phase based on hostnames

```

1: function FIRSTPHASE(incomingChunks, metaInformation)
2:   let sourceChunks be a mapping from hostnames
3:     to chunks on that host
4:   let sinkRanks be a mapping from hostnames
5:     to source rank ids running on that host
6:   for hostname  $\leftarrow$  available hostnames do
7:     let chunks  $\leftarrow$  sourceChunks[hostname]
8:     let ranks  $\leftarrow$  sinkRanks[hostname]
9:     if ranks =  $\emptyset$  then                                      $\triangleright$  No sink process on this host
10:      Report chunks as leftover chunks
11:     else
12:       Assign chunks to ranks,
13:       using an adequate implementation of the second phase
14:     end if
15:   end for
16: end function

```

Algorithm 1 will first sort incoming chunks by host of provenance and also processes of the reading application by host that they are running on. This way, we associate chunks with processes that they should be distributed to. The algorithm iterates the present hosts and uses an implementation of the second phase of the algorithm to achieve a complete distribution of chunks over the subset of chosen process ranks. Care must be taken if the set of destination ranks for some chunks is empty: This means that one node is fully occupied with only the writing application and no instance is present to read the produced data. In this case, the coupled codes have been configured in a way that is unfit for use of this algorithm and the chunks are reported as leftovers.

In the analogous situation where a node is occupied by the reading application, this node is not going to receive data by application of this algorithm. Optimal performance can hence only be guaranteed by configuring the coupled simulation properly, correctness is in any case guaranteed by application of the second phase.

For cases when usage of the first phase is not intended, we implement a dummy version of the first phase that reports all chunks as unassigned, delegating all work to the second phase. We present three different possible implementations for the second phase.

Slice the complete dataset Since datasets have known sizes, one possibility is pre-assigning regions in that dataset to reading ranks. This comes close to the

conventional approach of explicitly selecting chunks to load, including advantages and disadvantages. Algorithm 2 will assign each reading rank a region in the dataset in form of a hypercube and then intersect the available chunks with that dataset to determine a rank’s chunks to load. While the distribution of data over the reading application’s parallel processes will be guaranteed to be as fair as possible, data will in the worst case be read in an $m \times n$ pattern where m is the number of chunks and n the number of reading ranks. This means that each chunk is accessed by each reading process.

Algorithm 2 Second phase based on slicing the complete dataset

```

1: function SECONDPHASE1(partialAssignment, destinationRanks, datasetExtent)
2:   Split the dataset into hypercubes such that
3:     each destination rank is assigned exactly one cube
4:   let cube  $\leftarrow$  current rank’s assigned cube
5:   for chunk  $\leftarrow$  leftover chunks do
6:     chunk  $\leftarrow$  intersect chunk with cube
7:     if chunk is non-zero in all dimensions then
8:       Assign chunk to current rank
9:     end if
10:  end for
11: end function

```

Round Robin Other than the previous algorithm, the round Robin based implementation will not slice the incoming chunks at all, guaranteeing a read pattern that is very close to the form that data is produced in. Algorithm 3 will simply distribute the incoming chunks over the reading ranks without further taking into regard chunk sizes. Usage of this approach should hence be restricted to cases where chunks are known to be of a form suitable for such a distribution, i.e. of roughly equal size and their number should be a multiple of the number of reading ranks.

Slice Incoming Chunks This approach tries to combine the advantages of the first two approaches. The rough proceeding is to calculate an ideal amount of data per rank, slice the incoming chunks such that this size is not exceeded and then distribute those size-fitted chunks across the reading ranks. The last step is non-trivial and an instance of the NP-complete bin-packing problem [1]. Greedy approximation algorithms are commonly used to approach this problem. We describe a simple algorithm that greedily approximates this problem within a factor of 2, i.e. each rank gets assigned at worst double the ideal amount.

Algorithm 4 on the next page first measures the total extent *ext* of the data to be distributed. The ideal amount per rank is then $\frac{ext}{N}$. The undistributed chunks are

Algorithm 3 Second phase based on the round Robin approach

```
1: function SECONDPHASE2(partialAssignment, destinationRanks)
2:   let  $N \leftarrow \text{sizeof}(\textit{destinationRanks})$ 
3:   let currentRank  $\leftarrow 1$ 
4:   for chunk  $\leftarrow$  unassigned chunks do
5:     Assign chunk to rank destinationRanks[i]
6:      $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
7:     if  $i > N$  then
8:        $i \leftarrow 1$ 
9:     end if
10:  end for
11: end function
```

Algorithm 4 Second phase by slicing the incoming chunks

```
function SECONDPHASE3(partialAssignment, destinationRanks)
  let  $N \leftarrow$  number of destinationRanks
  let  $ext \leftarrow \sum_{\text{unassigned chunks}}$  (extent of chunk)
  split unassigned chunks into subchunks of size at most  $\frac{ext}{N}$ 
  let  $L \leftarrow$  list of those subchunks, sorted from largest to smallest
  let  $A \leftarrow$  array of length  $2N$ , containing assigned chunks
   $\triangleright$  each slot can hold a size of  $\frac{ext}{N}$ 
  for  $i \leftarrow 1, \dots, 2N$  do
    for chunk  $\leftarrow L$  in decreasing order do
      if slot  $i$  can additionally hold chunk then
        Add chunk to slot  $A[i]$ 
      else
        continue
      end if
    end for
    Remove assigned chunks from  $L$ , keeping order
  end for
   $\triangleright$  At this point, all chunks are assigned (see proof)
  return array  $A'$  where  $\forall i \in 1, \dots, N: A'[i] = A[i] \cup A[N + i]$ 
end function
```

split into subchunks of at most this size. This is the only splitting of chunks that the algorithm performs. The heart of the algorithm is described by distributing these chunks greedily over not N , but $2N$ chunks with capacity $\frac{ext}{N}$. The slots are iterated, and each slot is filled up with chunks that have not been distributed yet, preferring large chunks over small ones. In the end, pairs of slots are built and merged into one slot each, guaranteeing the aforementioned occupancy up to at worst twice the ideal amount.

We prove that the presented algorithm will actually assign all chunks in the central for-loop. Assume for contradiction a chunk of size x has not found place in any of the $2N$ bins. At least one slot must exist among the $2N$ slots that is filled strictly below half its capacity. Otherwise, the total fill status would be $\geq 2N \cdot (\frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{ext}{N}) = ext$, i.e. every data item would have been distributed.

- If $x \leq \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{ext}{N}$, the chunk would fit in this slot.
- If $x \geq \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{ext}{N}$, the greedy nature of the algorithm would have preferred to put the chunk of size x into the slot over the smaller chunks that are occupying it.

Both situations cannot occur and the correctness of the algorithm is hence proven by contradiction.

Other than the round Robin algorithm, we obtain a guarantee on data balancing, and other than the approach that slices the incoming dataset, we get guarantees that the incoming chunks are not arbitrarily subdivided, but instead at most sliced into fixed-sized subchunks. Both guarantees are weaker than the guarantees given by the algorithm that takes care only of the one problem and ignores the other.

Furthermore, this algorithm will achieve a balanced distribution of chunks in situations when simply slicing the incoming dataset will not suffice. This is the case when the written chunks do not cover the complete dataset. Especially will slicing the incoming dataset not be a suitable plugin algorithm for the implementation of the first phase of chunk distribution based on hostnames. In line 13 of algorithm 1, only that subset of the whole dataset will be distributed that has been produced on the currently inspected node. While slicing the whole dataset along the reading ranks on that node will still yield a correct result, an extremely unbalanced distribution is likely from this approach. Using the Round-Robin based algorithm may or may not yield a balanced distribution based on the pattern of data production. This leaves among the presented algorithms only algorithm 4 as an approach with guarantees for balanced distribution of data.

4.3 Implementation in a writer: PIConGPU

The legacy IO methods in PIConGPU are implemented in terms of plugins writing directly to HDF5 [33] and ADIOS1 [27]. Both share a common basic structure, producing data in a species-by-species fashion. We port this implementation to a more generic description in terms of the openPMD API.

The new IO landscape available in PIConGPU is depicted in figure 4.5. Green lines show the IO plugins that have been previously present, blue lines show implementations that have been made over the course of this Master’s Thesis. While the openPMD API has a JSON backend, it is not usable from PIConGPU since it is serial-only but PIConGPU makes use of the Message Passing Interface.

Figure 4.5: IO landscape in PIConGPU

From an engineering perspective, this brings the benefit of increased maintainability. Next to lifting the necessity to implement the openPMD standard manually from the developer, this implementation also decouples data description from storage description, allowing to merge two very similar plugins into only one such plugin.

The major motivation for implementing this plugin is the improved extensibility achieved in implementing the openPMD plugin. By expressing data not directly to the IO backend, but instead in a data DSL in the problem domain, we obtain a more flexible plugin that is able to support future backend features of the openPMD API with ideally no, but at most relatively few changes.

Implementing a streaming workflow on the writer’s site is a mostly straightforward task. The writing code can decide how data is structured and organized into single streaming packets. While the writing code should take care that the output data has some easily-readable structure, such a structure is mostly implicitly present

for most filesystem-based IO methods. In PIconGPU, lifting the filesystem-based openPMD plugin to a streaming-based one consists in adding an `advance` call after each written species / field type to mark a “barrier” between single sent packets.

On the other hand, implementing a workflow where each streaming packet contains a complete physical region would require a much more pervasive rewrite of the logic in the IO plugin.

4.4 Implementation in a reader: GAPD

Implementing a streaming workflow in the data sink is comparatively more challenging. Unlike with filesystem-based layouts where data can be randomly accessed, we cannot be completely agnostic with respect to the writing code. A sink consumes data in a certain pattern and this pattern must be made compatible with the order of data arrival.

The extreme opposite of being agnostic concerning the producer code would be to tailor the reading procedures to one concrete producer. We choose a middle-ground: The data sink sets up a number of requirements for the incoming stream. As long as the data source upholds these requirements, the stream can be read by the sink.

Since GAPD is relatively free in allowing data parallelism as necessary, we set up only two requirements – one that *must* be fulfilled and one that *should* be fulfilled for performance reasons.

1. *Each single particle must be completely contained in one packet.* It is illegal for a particle’s data to be spread across several packets as this can in general only be handled by the sink through accumulating data until all data is present.
2. *The sub-chunking of a record’s datasets should be equivalent.* Given two datasets x, y pertaining to the same record and indices i, j contained in these datasets. If $x[i]$ and $x[j]$ form part of the same chunk within x , so should $y[i]$ and $y[j]$ within y . This is not a hard requirement, but fulfilling it helps performance. The reason is as follows: It is in general most resource effective to query data along the writer’s chunking. A single rank in the parallel simulation computed by GAPD needs to have full information on a particle that it processes. Hence, if a chunk of dataset x is loaded on a rank, this same chunk must also be loaded from dataset y . If this chunk is not actually present within dataset y in that form, GAPD will still be able to load it, but at the expense of requiring full $n \times m$ communication patterns at worst.

By setting up requirements in the described way, we create an interface for pipelined processing of a single iteration in GAPD. We note that the implementation

in GAPD does currently not make use of this, but instead accumulates a single iteration’s data before starting computation. There are two reasons for this: On the one hand, while definitely useful in general, for our current workflow, such a pipelined processing *within* GAPD is not necessary since our data source is PIconGPU whose IO plugin we implement to output a complete particle species at once. Hence, data does not arrive in such a way that pipelining would have an effect (excluding for now the case that a simulation produces several kinds of particle species). Secondly, GAPD itself outside the new IO plugin currently assumes that all data is given at once and does not natively support pipelining. This is no issue, since we strive to solve such problems not by modifying single applications, but instead through the coupling of codes, as is shown in figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Envisioned workflow for pipeline parallel processing

Modification of GAPD to meet our needs can be avoided by splitting the task at hand into a further separate tool that reads data arriving sequentially and performs the final accumulation that would otherwise need to be hardcoded into the application. Our implementation of stream reading within GAPD including the previously defined requirements is sufficient to support such a setup. To reach such a configuration, implementation of streaming IO output in GAPD as well as the implementation of an appropriate accumulation tool are necessary, both not contained in the scope of this Master’s Thesis. This will allow a more fine-grained pipeline parallel processing without having to make GAPD aware of the fact that only subsets of the complete iteration are computed.

Despite this current restriction, application-level pipeline parallelism between PIconGPU and GAPD at a granularity defined by iteration sizes is still naturally present in our streaming setup.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

Since the motivation for a streaming workflow has largely been driven out of necessity to avoid IO barriers, evaluation is due to what extent this goal has been fulfilled. Additionally, in a loosely coupled setup, proper usage of hardware becomes a nontrivial challenge. Requirements induced by the single applications' compute performance on the one hand and by communication performance on the other are – while not *necessarily* opposing goals – a challenge to fulfill at the same time. Proper scaling of applications to fit one another becomes mandatory in order not to create a bottleneck causing underutilization of allocated hardware.

We will first give a short overview of single targets for performance measurement that our evaluation is going to cover. After this, we discuss the strategy that we use to approach benchmarking. This is needed, since we execute a simulation consisting of heterogeneous codes on heterogeneous hardware, leaving us with too large of a margin for experimentation to cover exhaustively without a strategy. This discussion will cover parameters that we want to find decision upon *before* starting the benchmarks as well as parameters that need to be optimized dynamically by running a benchmark. Thus having found a choice in the values that we want to learn from a benchmark, we execute the benchmarks and evaluate their results.

5.1 Targets of benchmarking

Even if concentrating on time measurements, there is no single approach at benchmarking a heterogeneous simulation that involves more than one code communicating together. This section shall shortly investigate a number of different options, including their advantages and drawbacks.

Complete simulation Probably the most obvious option is to benchmark the complete simulation consisting of all codes involved. While the result of such a

benchmark is likely to be very interesting for an end-user who wants a simulation to finish as quickly as possible, this value gives little information about the actual runtime behavior and the interaction of codes with each other.

Time to complete one of the involved codes The roughest approach for a one-sided benchmark, targeting solely one of the involved applications is to measure the time necessary for one complete simulation to complete, including IO as well as computation time. Performing measurements not only for the IO parts of the simulation is imperative, since mapping several codes onto hardware will inevitably also impact computation performances. Ideally, all involved codes should be dimensioned such that their time requirements are roughly equivalent and one slow code does not block the other, faster one. Under these ideal circumstances, this metric should be equivalent to the time to end the complete simulation, comprising all involved codes. We strive to reach such circumstances.

IO performance As mentioned in the introduction, simulations increasingly grow to be IO-limited. This was one of the major motivations for this Thesis and hence we want to know how much time is spent by simulations in IO sections. A challenge in this is the on-the-fly nature of a streaming simulation. Besides the actual movement of data, time spent in streaming IO procedures includes also waiting for the other code to catch up and data preparation. The latter again may include reading data from accelerator units such as GPUs, as well as aggregation of metadata across several ranks.

Performance of raw data movement The actual stream of data from one code to another one bears different implications on the hardware mapping than the other aforementioned components of the IO procedures. While rank-local data preparation, including GPU-to-CPU copies shows near-perfect weak scaling, a deciding factor in application-wide performance of a loosely-coupled simulation lies in the weak scaling behavior of data transport between applications. In order to evaluate the fitness of the hardware mapping at stake, it becomes necessary to single out the performance of those operations. The asynchronous nature mandates that the latency of such operations is less crucial than their throughput.

5.2 Strategy

Before executing benchmarks, discussion is necessary what parameters in a simulation setup will have influence on a benchmark and how to approach the choice of such parameters.

5.2.1 Simulation parameters

Given that the particle-in-cell algorithm is a very generic algorithm and PIconGPU hence also to be understood as a generic framework to derive concrete instances of the particle-in-cell algorithm, parameterized at compile-time as well as at runtime, the question arises which simulation exactly to run. Similarly, within GAPD, parameters must be found at which to perform the analysis.

Realistically, in a physical workflow, the simulation of interest to be performed is largely fixed and only adaptable to computational requirements up to a certain margin. We will hence keep the actual simulation being run consistent across the benchmarks. A PIconGPU simulation that lends itself for this purpose is the *Laser Wakefield* simulation [32]. This is a well-established and tested instance of PIconGPU that amasses large amounts of data and allows for feasible testing at low as well as at high scales. For GAPD, we use the *Ewald sphere mode* to construct points in reciprocal space.

There will be a number of simulation parameters that we will vary within our benchmarks. Firstly, we will scale the size of the grid under scrutiny to test for parallel weak scaling behavior. Secondly, we will vary the temporal resolution, i.e. the number of steps that PIconGPU performs between two data dumps. This allows for testing to what extent concurrently executed components block one another. When dumping infrequently, we expect PIconGPU to block the execution of GAPD which will take longer times waiting for new data to arrive. Conversely, when dumping frequently, we expect GAPD to block PIconGPU since GAPD must process one iteration before consuming the next one. Additionally, in the latter case, the host-side IO routines within PIconGPU are expected to block the device-side accelerated simulation.

5.2.2 IO Stack and Hardware mapping

The hardware stack in usage – processors, transport and storage – will naturally influence the benchmark. By being implemented in terms of the performance-portable Cupla and Alpaka libraries, we are free to execute PIconGPU and GAPD on GPU as well as on CPU hardware. Given that one of the core motivations for a streaming workflow in PIconGPU was the fact that the particle-in-cell simulation has become fast enough through GPU acceleration that slow-down through IO started becoming a problem, we will concentrate on executing PIconGPU as “conductor” at the highest speed possible – i.e. with GPU acceleration – and adjust the succeeding analysis pipeline to keep up with its speed. This way, we keep true to our aim not to induce slow-down on the initial simulation through IO. The hardware choice for GAPD will be determined through benchmarking.

Next to processing hardware, the choice of storage and transport hardware also

bears implications on the runtime behavior of a coupled simulation. To provide for a fair baseline to compare the streaming workflow against, we use SSD storage for fast disk-based write and read access. ADIOS2 currently supports data staging via communication networks (sockets and RDMA) while node-local communication via shared memory is still under development. This makes inter-node communication hardware such as Infiniband our hardware of choice for streaming workflows. We will further discuss the layout of our communication in the following point.

5.2.3 Data transport and efficient computation as opposing goals

In a loosely coupled simulation, each writer rank will produce a number of data chunks for the reader to process. In a single streaming step, this number may be any non-negative integer, including zero. Depending on the running simulations, we should expect data to not necessarily be of equal size per rank. This is the case in the particle-in-cell algorithm where the physical space is split into chunks of equal size. It depends on the concrete simulation performed on how many particles are present in one chunk. Since in parallelized implementations of this algorithm such as PIConGPU, the ranks are distributed along the single chunks, there will in general be writer ranks that send more data than others.

The reader will now need to distribute this data across its ranks. Since GAPD is an embarrassingly-parallel simulation, we are in general free to tune this phase according to performance necessities. As long as IO performance is non-critical and our optimization efforts go solely into the calculation performance of the slave simulation, the incoming data can be trivially split into m chunks of (nearly) equal size, m being the number of ranks in the slave simulation. This way, we can guarantee an equal utilization of resources per rank. This corresponds with algorithm 2 on page 42.

As soon as IO performance gets critical, this approach may bring runtime penalties with itself since it does not consider at all the way that data is chunked. We obtain as a worst-case a full $m \times n$ streaming (m being the number of ranks in the master simulation) where each master rank will stream to several (up to n) slave ranks and each slave rank will read from several (up to m) master ranks.

The next, more IO-sensitive approach is found in algorithm 3 on page 43 which will simply distribute data in a round-robin manner without further chunk distinction. There are two ways that make chunks non-equals, making this algorithm unfit for global chunk assignment. We shall shortly investigate both.

Chunk sizes As mentioned previously, not all chunks are necessarily of equal size.

Hence, we favor a solution that assigns written chunks to reading ranks in a balanced manner.

Writer rank Each written chunk stems from one writer rank. In order to ensure data proximity it becomes necessary to pay attention to data provenance. A flexible approach that can be used to leverage the other approaches lies in defining groups of reader and writer ranks such that reader ranks are only allowed to read data from writer ranks within their respective group. Inside one group, one of the aforementioned methods may be used to distribute data. This corresponds to algorithm 1 on page 41.

If ranks are distributed across compute nodes such that each node runs instances of the master as well as of the slave, this method can then be used to run a simulation where both simulations cooperate only within a node, but not across several nodes.

We conclude three desirable properties for a chunk assignment:

proximity Data should be loaded from nearby – ideally from the same node, else from a nearby node to reduce contention on the network.

balancing Data should be distributed in a balanced manner to reading processes.

alignment Chunks should be loaded in roughly the same manner that they are written to avoid reassembling of data in the backend and $m \times n$ communication patterns.

If data is written in an imbalanced manner, as is the case in PICongPU, achieving *proximity* will naturally conflict with achieving a *balanced* assignment. Next up, we will discuss strategies that fulfill the upper properties to mixed extents.

5.2.4 Strategies to be tested for chunk distribution

Before performing the actual measurements, we define a number of strategies that we want to test:

(1) **disk-based** We use the BP4 engine in ADIOS2 to dump data to disk and load that data into GAPD. SSD storage is used to provide for fast read and write access. The codes are executed fully sequentially, i.e. the data sink (GAPD) is launched only after the data source (PICongPU) finishes to compute.

This means that no application-level parallelism is used in this benchmark, allowing each code to fully utilize all allocated resources without sharing. For throughput measurement purposes, this implies that we can reduce filesystem contention on the accessed folders by writers and readers, yielding more precise results.

(2) one code per node The following benchmarks in this listing are all performed in streaming fashion via ADIOS2’s SST engine, making use of RDMA networks.

In this benchmark, each compute node is used exclusively by the data source (PConGPU) or the data sink (GAPD). Chunks are assigned to reading ranks by virtue of the bin-packing approximation algorithm (see alg. 4 on page 43).

This achieves an *aligned* and *balanced* distribution at the cost of having no *proximity* – neither are the codes executed together, nor does the algorithm in use consider locality.

(3) codes collaborating per node Unlike the previous benchmark, this one puts running instances of PConGPU together with running instances of GAPD per node.

To figure out whether this form of locality will actually make an impact, this benchmark is split in three: Next to assigning each reading code with exactly those chunks that have been written on the same node (approach **(3a)**), we additionally perform test runs that ignore node locality, using two alternative approaches: Firstly, we distribute chunks by simply slicing the complete dataset into equal-sized pieces (refer to alg. 2 on page 42, approach **(3b)**) as well as by distributing chunks via the bin-packing algorithm (alg. 4 on page 43, approach **(3c)**).

Approach (3a) will achieve a distribution that strictly conforms to chunk *proximity*, at the cost of *balancing* which is only achieved in a per-node manner. *Alignment* is achieved. By distributing processes by both codes across available hardware in the same order, we hope to achieve a *quasi-local* chunk distribution from approach (3b) where data does not necessarily come from the same node, but from a nearby node. It will yield a strictly *balanced* distribution at the cost of having no *alignment*. Approach (3c) provides no *proximity* guarantees on the distribution of equal-sized chunks, provoking more chaos in the communication network. It will, however, adhere to the chunks’ *alignment* and data *balancing* is achieved approximatively.

Table 5.1 on the next page gives an overview.

5.3 Benchmarks

With the above strategies defined, we can now put them to application. We try to solve two questions:

Table 5.1: Strategies and their achieved goals

	(2)	(3a)	(3b)	(3c)
proximity	no	yes	approximately	no
balancing	yes	per node	yes	approximately
alignment	yes	yes	no	yes

1. To what extent has the approach taken in this Thesis been successful in reducing the filesystem bottleneck?
2. How should a coupled simulation be parameterized – hardware and simulation parameters alike – to achieve good resource usage? Is such a configuration possible?

Relevant for both questions is the throughput achieved during raw data transfer which we will test first. This will give us a first impression on bottlenecks and shall decide whether we will focus on optimizing data throughput or on optimizing execution times through usage of a more balanced distribution. With these results in mind, we use performance measurements to configure a simulation to make use of allocated resources without wastage. Potential for conflict is found at two places:

Between PIconGPU and GAPD Depending on the frequency of data dumps from PIconGPU, either code may block the other one in execution. We will first strive to find a configuration where both codes are dimensioned in such a way that no such underutilization of resources happens.

Between host-side and device-side computations PIconGPU runs its computations mostly on the GPU, while the IO plugin is executed host-side in concurrent fashion. We will determine what impact IO has on the running simulation. This will clarify whether the IO bottleneck has been successfully reduced.

5.3.1 Throughput

We first perform throughput-oriented testing. We will always give the **throughput per parallel rank**. The total throughput can be approximately recovered from these figures by multiplying them with the number of parallel ranks¹. Coming from

¹Since we use the median and not the average to obtain the throughput per rank, the results from such a calculation might vary statistically from the real throughput. We will later argue why we deem this to be the more representative statistic.

disk-based workflows, our baseline to compare against is given by writing to and reading from filesystems. Tests are run on the Taurus compute cluster, located at Technische Universität Dresden.

We begin measurement on the K20x partition of the Taurus compute cluster. While the NVIDIA Tesla K20x GPUs are at this point rather dated – first presented in 2012 –, we do for now not target compute performance for our measurements. Additionally, this compute partition has fast connection to the SDD storage, allowing for fair benchmark results.

In order to benchmark the scaling behavior, we perform the benchmark at different levels of parallelism. For the disk-based benchmark, the numbers of parallel processes are 4, 16 and 32. Since in the other two benchmarks, i.e. the streaming-based ones, it is mandatory to execute the two applications concurrently, we execute them at parallelity levels of 4, 16 and 24 in order to fit these processes on the compute partition. On the K20x partition, we test strategies (1), (2), (3a) and (3b). For the latter two strategies, we put one instance of PIconGPU and GAPD per node respectively. With two GPUs available per node, this gives each code one GPU to perform hardware-accelerated computations.

Figure 5.1: Throughput per rank for some selected benchmarks on Taurus K20x

Figure 5.1 shows the measured throughput per rank for each of the described approaches at their highest level of parallelism. Since PIconGPU will not produce particle data in every rank, GAPD instances running on the same node will not load data in the node-local approach. Those ranks do not show data in the diagram. It turns out that the measured throughput of those benchmarks with global communication, i.e. the filesystem-based one and the streaming workflow with global chunk mapping (strategies (1) and (2)), will suffer from outliers. The fewest number of

outliers is found in the node-local approach (strategy (3a)), confirming that we produce a minimal amount of contention between parallel processes with this strategy. As expected, the values achieved by approach (3b) fall into roughly the same dimensions as by approach (3a), but show some increased scattering due to a lower, but still existing level of data locality.

The complete results are given in figure 5.2. Due to the observed outliers in large parts of the data, we conclude for the median as an adequate statistic to obtain meaningful results.

Figure 5.2: Measured median throughput per rank on the K20x partition of Taurus by parallelism level

As expected, the filesystem-based workflow provides for the lowest data throughput, ranging between roughly 100 MB s^{-1} and 900 MB s^{-1} throughput per rank in the median. We notice a tendency towards degradation of throughput with increasing numbers of parallel processes, indicating a lack of scalability for this workflow. Tests at parallelism level 48 will unfortunately crash during file writing.

The mapping of codes to hardware shows an impact on measured throughput. We have previously explained that the more consistent values across parallel processes for the node-local chunk mapping can be explained with the tidier communication pattern resulting from this strategy. By reducing contention on the interconnect structure, we create a more scalable approach that performs heavy communication exclusively within one compute node. This contention does not show effect for low levels of parallelism, actually giving approach (2) an advantage over approaches (3a)

and (3b) at low scale. We observe performance degradation from approach (2) with increasing parallelism while the other two streaming strategies only start paying off at higher scale. In order to confirm these observations and assumptions, we will repeat this benchmark on the ML partition that allows for scaling to higher levels of parallelism.

We observe very similar behavior from approaches (3a) and (3b) with some expected performance losses in approach (3b). Even though approach (3a) will keep communication local to one node, the technology stack used underneath is still the same in both test runs, allowing to observe exactly these results. At the time of writing this, a node-local streaming engine based on communication via shared memory for ADIOS2 is still under development. By implementing distribution strategies flexibly, the openPMD API as well as our coupled setup are prepared to leverage the performance benefits from using such an engine upon availability, making starker differences between these two approaches likely. We can conclude that node-locality does (currently) not show a large impact on throughput as long as the capacity of the communication network is not reached.

Figure 5.3: Measured median throughput per rank on the ML partition of Taurus by parallelism level

We perform test runs on the ML compute partition of the Taurus cluster, testing for strategies (2), (3a) and (3c). Since this compute partition has a slower connection to the SSD filesystem, we do not perform large-scale filesystem tests. The results can be seen in figure 5.3. We measure a throughput of $\sim 20 \text{ MB s}^{-1}$ upon writing, no other filesystem test is able to execute without crashing in the given configuration. The ML partition, offering a number of six GPUs per node, allows us to put our

tests to a larger scale to confirm our previous observations and assumptions. We run our tests with up to 64 parallel processes for PIconGPU and for GAPD, thus using 128 GPUs. In strategies (3a) and (3c), PIconGPU and GAPD share resources per node, with each code using three GPUs.

The qualitative results can be compared to the results gained on the K20x partition, with approach (2) yielding a higher throughput at lower scales, while showing continuously degrading performance with higher levels of parallelism. Approaches (3a) and (3c) will again perform worse at a low scale. Since the expected “chaotic” effects on the communication network are not reached with only few parallel ranks, performance of both approaches is relatively similar in the beginning. Interestingly, all three approaches show similar throughput at 32 parallel ranks, with the expected scaling behavior being most clearly observable at 64 ranks. Here, approach (3a) clearly profits from its good scalability while (3c) will suffer from the global $m \times n$ communication pattern. Strategy (2)’s throughput continues to sink, ranging between the other two approaches’ results.

Figure 5.4: Throughput per rank on Taurus ML

Figure 5.4 gives more insight into the throughput values achieved per rank for the test runs with 64×2 parallel ranks. We notice that approaches (2) and (3c) both achieve an increased throughput beginning from rank 48. Both approaches use the bin-packing algorithm to distribute chunks globally and in both test series, this algorithm assigned to the ranks 48 through 63 the leftover smaller chunks (three per rank) while all previous ranks loaded each one large chunk of data. We conclude

that in an $m \times n$ communication pattern, the network can react more flexibly to smaller sent chunks than to large ones. We stress that this does not lead to the conclusion that smaller packet sizes are to be preferred over large ones. Much rather in a situation where many small packets are sent, the communication network may prefer the smaller packets over the larger ones.

Strategy (3a) shows a less consistent behavior than on the K20x partition. We relate this to the fact that in these test series, there is now additionally more parallelism per node than on the K20x compute partition where we ran only one instance of each code per node. While there is a baseline at $\sim 2000 \text{ MB s}^{-1}$, we observe further a number of spikes, reaching up to a throughput of above 7000 MB s^{-1} on rank 42. We observe that these outliers are usually shared between all instances running on the same node. Upon inspection of the chunk distribution, we notice that these outliers are related to relatively little data exchanged (~ 20 to ~ 40 million particles per iteration and rank instead of ~ 49 million on average) on that node and on two nodes due to relatively imbalanced chunk mappings found by the bin-packing approximation that is used to distribute data per node. The only outliers going clearly below the baseline of 2000 MB s^{-1} are found on ranks 48 through 50. This node produces an above-average amount of data (~ 67 million particles per iteration and rank with the average at ~ 49 million) and while the chunks are fairly distributed across these three ranks, the node’s communication network seems to favor rank 49 at the cost of rank 48 and 50’s throughputs.

5.3.2 Coupling PIconGPU with GAPD

Moving away from throughput-oriented testing, we try to set up a coupled simulation that sensibly makes use of the allocated resources. As mentioned in the introduction (section 5.2), optimizing data transfer and optimizing calculation time can prove to be contradicting goals. This is demonstrated in figure 5.5 on the facing page. While strategy (3a) provides for the best scaling behavior with regards to data transport, it will inherit to GAPD the data imbalances inherent in the particle-in-cell algorithm. With all ranks having to wait for the one rank that takes the longest time to finish computation, such imbalances prove to have a negative impact on compute time. Strategies (2) and (3b) will both distribute chunks equally among reading instances of GAPD, leading to equivalent runtime costs between both approaches. Since we have previously observed comparable data transport performance between strategies (3a) and (3b) and the compute performance benefit achieved by (3b) is greater than its negative data transport performance impact, we conclude to further pursue this strategy.

We inspect in more detail the compute costs of GAPD. This code receives as input a number of N_a atoms in real space, distributes them to M CPU threads, and

Figure 5.5: GAPD compute times per iteration by used strategy – the effect of imbalanced data distribution. Short of 49 million particles are loaded per rank and iteration, 1305 points are constructed in k -space. Executed using 16 ranks on Taurus ML using GPU acceleration.

computes the diffraction intensity I at the scattering vector \mathbf{q} . The most compute-intensive step is the computation of the structure factor $F(\mathbf{q})$, given by

$$F(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_a} f_j \exp(2\pi i \mathbf{q} \cdot r_j)$$

In here, r_j denotes the position of atom j in real space and f_j its *atomic scattering factor*, mandated by the element that the atom forms part of. The unparallelized computation of this vector requires $N_a \cdot q$ iterations. Computation on M parallel ranks requires $\frac{N_a}{M} \cdot q$ iterations per rank, resulting in M partial vectors to be summed in a collective operation. One iteration is implemented in the non-GPU-accelerated version of GAPD using eight floating point multiplications. When loading 49 million particles (per rank) and calculating a (very moderate) number of 1305 points in reciprocal space, this leaves roughly half a trillion floating point operations per rank and iteration which explains the non-negligible compute costs even with GPU acceleration. We conclude that using the GPU-accelerated implementation of GAPD is mandatory to construct a coupled simulation-analysis workflow where GAPD has a chance to keep pace with PIconGPU.

To obtain a first impression on the runtime behavior of such a coupled simulation, we measure the waiting times for a streaming setup on the K20x partition of Taurus. This setup contains four ranks for PIconGPU as well as for GAPD and uses strategy

(a) PICongPU waiting times, dumping every hundredth timestep

(b) GAPD waiting times, dumping every hundredth timestep

(c) PICongPU waiting times, dumping every timestep

(d) GAPD waiting times, dumping every timestep

Figure 5.6: Waiting times for PICongPU as well as GAPD. Depicted is a simulation on K20x with four reader and writer ranks, ~ 31 million particles per rank and timestep.

(3b) to distribute chunks equally. Two “extreme” setups are tested – firstly, we dump data only in every hundredth timestep and secondly in every single timestep. Two notable effects are visible in figure 5.6a: On the one hand, the nature of the particle-in-cell algorithm shows relatively clearly by the visible spikes, alternating between parallel ranks. These spikes are caused by ranks that do not produce particle data in a step and reach the waiting barrier faster. Since particle data does not stay on one rank across different steps, these spikes are seen in every parallel rank. On the other hand, there is a baseline at zero seconds, indicating that PIconGPU is in this setup not blocked by GAPD. We note that up to ten seconds of waiting time per spike seems suspiciously long and we will further investigate that. Figure 5.6b shows the waiting behavior of the same coupled simulation in the case of GAPD. Only one rank is depicted, since GAPD by computing an embarrassingly parallel problem shows the same waiting behavior on every parallel rank. We notice that GAPD will constantly wait for close to ten seconds, indicating that PIconGPU is blocking the execution of GAPD in this setup.

Figures 5.6c and 5.6d show the inverse blocking behavior. While GAPD can read data instantly after finishing to compute, PIconGPU will always need to wait for at least twenty seconds before GAPD accepts further data.

Figure 5.7: Waiting times for PIconGPU as well as GAPD. Depicted is a simulation on K20x with four reader and writer ranks, ~ 31 million particles per rank and timestep. Data is dumped every hundredth timestep. These measurements improve upon those in figure 5.6 by means of avoiding costly buffer initializations and reallocations within ADIOS2.

Upon calculation of the “sweet spot” that minimizes both codes’ waiting times, we notice that the complete IO routines take an unusually long time between 30 and 40 seconds. This time is not spent during the actual IO events which we benchmarked previously, but during data preparation and this also explains the large spikes that we mentioned in figure 5.6a. We trace the issue back to reallocations being performed during data preparation in ADIOS2. Within ADIOS2, this is related to the fact that the BP3 serialization engine used by the SST engine allocates and resizes new buffers in every single streaming step. While the serialization engine for SST is currently being rewritten to make use of BP4 serialization, also targeting exactly this issue, we avoid the problem for the moment by manually setting buffer sizes and also by sending each iteration as one single packet to reduce buffer initialization costs. This reduces the time spent by the IO routines down to between four and six seconds. This time is spent during the phases that all data written by the IO routine has to pass: Data is copied from device to host memory, rearranged to conform with the openPMD standard, serialized in the backend and written to transport. The last step in this pipeline, while asynchronous, may cause blocking behavior as soon as the queue limit has been reached. Additionally to this pipeline’s steps, buffer initialization takes between one and two seconds which we hope to eliminate once the improvements explained above have been finished in ADIOS2.

With this workaround implemented, we run again the same simulation with data dumps every hundredth timestep. It turns out that GAPD takes between two and three seconds to read one data dump (with the largest amount of time spent during conversion of data to the format required by GAPD) and in succession between 30 to 40 seconds to perform its computations. Conversely, PIconGPU takes between 41 to 43 seconds between two dumped iterations, hence a configuration is found where no code blocks the other. While we were able to speed up the IO routines in PIconGPU by roughly half a minute, the largest spikes in figure 5.6a were found at under ten seconds. This is explained by the fact that the asynchronous execution of IO alongside the simulation was able to hide part of the inefficiencies. For a visualization, refer to figure 5.7.

5.3.3 Computation versus IO

Having configured PIconGPU and GAPD not to block one another, we want to figure out how much the GPU-accelerated simulation in PIconGPU is blocked by activating IO procedures. Before performing dedicated measurements, we mention that in the previous simulation setup, the simulation was able to execute without being slowed down by performing IO: The time between two data dumps was between 41 and 43 seconds while IO routines finished between four and six seconds after invocation, indicating that performance has been compute-bound. Since CPU-side and GPU-side computations can be performed asynchronously, such a slow-down

Figure 5.8: PIconGPU compute time using 16 parallel ranks on Taurus ML and K20x. This measures raw calculation time without any IO, with streaming and disk-based IO when dumping every single time step. Raw IO time refers to the accumulated time that was spent during data transfer. Startup time is excluded. Note the logarithmic x -scale.

is only caused by performing IO procedures that take longer to execute than the computations leading up to the next data dump.

In order to make IO more critical, we perform again simulations that dump data in every single step. We execute simulations at sixteen parallel ranks, producing ~ 49 million particles per rank and iteration. Data is dumped to disk in one setup, in another setup to a reading instance of GAPD that we modify to perform no calculations at all. This way, the reader is always ready to consume further data. As baseline, we compute simulations that do not dump data at all. The resulting numbers are seen in figure 5.8. We compute 40 iterations. Since the Laser Wakefield simulation becomes more compute-intensive after ~ 1000 iterations, we compute 3000 iterations and use the time necessary for the last 40 iterations. On the other side, the SSD partition on Taurus does not allow for arbitrary amounts of data being written. We can dump 27 iterations within roughly 42 minutes which corresponds to 40 iterations in ~ 62 minutes. Roughly 1.2 TB are amassed during these 42 minutes, which at a partition capacity of 43 TB would fill the whole partition in roughly 25 h.

The simulation time for the streaming-based approach is around 8 minutes (5 minutes and 20 seconds on Taurus ML), yielding a speedup factor of 7.9. Encompassed in this time are 20 seconds of raw data transport (25 seconds on Taurus ML). Since the SST engine in ADIOS2 implements IO completely asynchronously, there is no slowdown by actual data transport on the running simulation. There is, however, a definite slowdown by performing IO as compared to a simulation running

without dumping any data. Raw computation of 40 iterations takes 16 seconds (four seconds on Taurus ML), meaning a slow-down through streaming IO by a factor of 29.5 (87.3 respectively). These values can be interpreted as the number of iterations that the simulation would need to compute between two data dumps such that IO does not slow down the running simulation. For comparison, we calculate a number of 235 iterations for the break-even point in the disk-based setup on K20x.

Figure 5.9: Time spent in the IO plugin

Figure 5.9 shows the time that the IO plugin spends during execution. The major time sink shows to be serialization with further profiling suggesting the extraction of metadata from the raw input to be cost-intensive. Additionally, a third of the serialization time is lost during initialization of the serialization buffer. Reevaluation will be due upon arrival of the rewritten serialization in the SST engine. This newly-written engine will allow for reuse of the serialization buffer across steps and for deferred consumption of input data. While the openPMD IO plugin in PIconGPU will automatically reap the benefits of reusing buffers, this is not quite as easy for deferred data consumption. In order to allow for execution also in environments with limited host memory, the IO plugin currently reuses its output buffers. Making use of deferred consumption however will require reverting this design choice to make more buffers visible to ADIOS2 at a single time step. As a result, it remains to be seen whether this performance bottleneck persists upon availability of the new serialization engine before changing the IO plugin to require more memory.

We conclude that the bottleneck in the streaming setup is found in CPU-side computations. Ignoring those computations, the bottleneck would be found in data transport with GPU-accelerated computations being the fastest of the previously mentioned components. We can confirm once more that in the setup found in the previous subsection, dumping data to GAPD every 100 iterations, does not slow the running simulation down.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Outlook

We have devised, implemented and put to test a framework for IO in scientific HPC simulations producing and consuming data according to the openPMD standard in a streaming fashion upon the openPMD API and ADIOS2. Runtime behavior, as well as scaling behavior, have been examined.

Our results have confirmed assumptions on scaling behavior, while at the same time having shown that concrete runtime behavior can be hard to predict and is subject to hardware and configuration details. It has hence been proven useful to implement flexibly interchangeable strategies for distribution of data from source to sink. This way, we were able to use different mappings of running instances to hardware and quickly react to circumstances altered this way. Also within the same mapping of instances to hardware, we were able to easily switch strategies for communication between loosely coupled instances.

It has been shown that both alterations – process mapping as well as chunk mapping – bear implications on data throughput with results that are at times difficult to predict, making benchmarking necessary before running a full-scale coupled simulation. In general, we observed that at low scales, running parallel processes of only one application per compute node resulted in higher throughput than sharing nodes between different codes. This behavior flipped with scaling where the effects of $m \times n$ communication became noticeable and showed dominating effects on throughput values. Strategies that purposefully maximized such communication chaos expectedly resulted in the worst scaling potential as opposed to other strategies.

There has been no clear-cut border between throughput results of node-local versus inter-node communication strategies. The IO stack that we used for benchmarking does at the moment not distinguish between both communication patterns and uses infrastructure designed for inter-node communication in both situations. By keeping communication flexible, we have prepared for the use of node-local com-

munication upon availability in the underlying IO framework ADIOS2. We have nonetheless been able to demonstrate that even during the use of inter-node communication networks, it will prove sensible to organize communication in a locality-aware manner to reduce contention.

While with usage of node-local communication infrastructure (i.e. through shared memory), making the codes comply with these increased demands on data distribution becomes mandatory for correctness, with our current setup, the major concern is performance. This leaves us with a looser margin for experimentation and we have shown that communication even across nodes can reach throughput values close to those achieved by strictly ensuring intra-node communication, if the communication pattern still respects a sensible measure of locality.

To this end, we did not implement a strategy explicitly aiming to achieve such a distribution, but used instead the strategy that globally split the dataset into hypercubes to distribute along reading ranks. Since we know that PIconGPU's IO plugin produces particle data with indices in rising order across MPI ranks, a side effect of this strategy is the observed effect of quasi-local distribution. A further topic of interest can hence be distribution strategies that make such a pattern explicit. The behavior implicitly achieved by the above method would become a design goal for such a strategy: While data should mainly be loaded from the same node, nearby nodes should also be taken into consideration for compromise if better data balancing can be achieved. Quick approximation of such a pattern is possible with the strategies already implemented: Instead of directly sorting chunks by host of provenance, compute nodes can be grouped into node groups of fixed size which can then be used as the basis for chunk distribution.

While we have not been able to put a node-local communication to testing, we have seen that data transfer is in our setup currently not critical and making compromises between compute time and data throughput has turned out more important than the sole optimization of throughput that would be achieved in a node-local setup.

If comparing only the time necessary for data transport and for GPU-side calculations, it turns out that with older compute hardware (NVIDIA Tesla K20x), the network can output data at a similar rate that it is produced by the simulation. With the more modern NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU, computation has been sped up, resulting in a factor of nearly seven between the time needed for outputting data as compared to the time needed for its computation, making the processing of only every seventh iteration feasible without slowing down the simulation. We note that our measurements confirm the current trend in HPC towards an increasing IO bottleneck, made apparent through increasingly efficient compute hardware.

Nonetheless, the performance bottleneck is found in neither of both, but instead in the CPU-side data preparation for transport. This signifies to us that a node-local

communication through shared memory is currently not to be considered a critical necessity. Still, using locality-respecting communication patterns has proven important independently from the communication technology to aid scaling performance.

Efforts should be put into improving the bottleneck found in CPU-side calculations. Fortunately, those computations exhibit the same form of weak scaling found also in the actual simulation, leaving us with a constant-factor challenge. On the downside, even after improving upon the currently rather slow serialization, the remaining data preparation pipeline provides for compute costs that easily outweigh the other potential bottlenecks in our setup. Should this bottleneck turn out critical, efforts to remove it may include the following measures:

GPU-to-GPU communication Similar to the way that disk-based communication sees wide-spread usage despite its intrinsic shortcomings not because alternatives do not exist, but because workflows do not exist, we currently take detours through the host-side despite the availability of GPU-to-GPU communication systems. Ecosystems such as NVIDIA GPUDirect need to be leveraged in the openPMD API for flexible IO that does not sacrifice performance. This Thesis has laid the fundament for a more direct IO in a streaming fashion and GPU-to-GPU streaming is one of the next logical steps in continuation on that path.

openPMD as an internal data structure We have seen that part of the time for data preparation is lost during conversion from application-specific ad-hoc formats to the format defined by the openPMD standard and implemented by the openPMD API. Performing such conversions is not only a computational, but also a developmental overhead which should be avoided in a longterm perspective. To this end, we observe that the openPMD API performs at its core two separate tasks:

1. Provide a straightforward description of particle-mesh data according to the openPMD standard.
2. Efficiently implement this standard in terms of interchangeable backends.

While implementation efforts have so far focused on workflows where this description is used in terms of performing IO, the potential of the openPMD API is not restricted to IO. By using the openPMD API to represent internal application data, compatibility with the openPMD standard is enforced, eliminating needs to convert data before usage.

With the work done in this Master’s Thesis, extending the openPMD API in the described way is expected to be a straightforward task through application of the *inline engine* in ADIOS2. This engine whose capabilities are currently

not used in the openPMD API’s implementation of the ADIOS2 backend is designed for communication within the same process, making it a candidate for the implementation of the openPMD API as the layout of choice for simulations’ internal data structures.

The effects of a new serialization backend in ADIOS2 have to be tested and evaluated upon availability.

We have been able to show in direct comparison to disk-based workflows that streaming IO drastically reduces the IO bottleneck already at low scale and enables good scalability beyond numbers that are already not feasible anymore for disk-based IO. While we were able to keep developmental overhead low by making the reuse of existing IO infrastructure possible, ideally already written with disk-based IO in mind using the openPMD API, applications will still need to encode a minimum of streaming semantics in order to leverage streaming-based technologies. We have defined such semantics generically in the openPMD API, resulting in a description of data movement that we hope to be usable across different implementations, and implemented those semantics in the ADIOS2 backend.

Making an application streaming-aware by adding such a description will in general imply the setup of an interface setting restrictions upon the format of arriving data. This necessity is intrinsic in the nature of streaming, since unlike in disk-based IO data sinks will see the effects of the data source’s strategy for data writing to a far greater extent. Good parallelizability of reading codes has proven useful to react to dynamically changing conditions.

It remains to be seen how chunk assignment strategies can be adapted to codes that do not allow for a completely randomized assignment of data, but instead have correctness-relevant requirements on data distribution across hardware. Depending on the code, distribution strategies that respect such requirements may or may not be feasible, compromising the flexibility of chunk assignment strategies and the easily-predictable behavior of random access.

While the bin-sorting based assignment strategy has in general shown to yield good results, single cases have been observed where the worst-case quality of the approximation (factor two within the optimal solution) has been reached while an optimal strategy would have been obvious. Adequate heuristics should be explored to further improve this approach’s reliability for a well-balanced distribution.

Next to the long-term outlook described above for physical simulations that use openPMD not solely for IO, but also internally, we describe further additional work that can be based on this Master’s Thesis.

A first, short-term contender within this category is the further exploitation of features in ADIOS2. We have so far used the engine in ADIOS2 that is explicitly designed for streaming between scientific HPC applications in mind, the *sustainable staging support* engine. While we have so far described workflows of simulation

pipelines where a clear relation between sources and sinks is apparent, *cooperating* simulations are also of interest. A simple example is the reorganization of data in external tools, to be fed back into the simulation. The SST engine explicitly supports such workflows by providing a Read/Write mode. This capability is currently not available from the openPMD API, but can be made available with relative ease given the work leading to this point.

We have so far not used other streaming engines in ADIOS2, but expect the openPMD API to be a direct beneficiary of the modular design in ADIOS2, ideally allowing the use of such engines without further change to the openPMD API interface. These engines are the InSituMPI engine, leveraging implementations of the *message passing interface* (MPI) available on the system and the *DataMan* engine, allowing for inter-cluster communication via *wide area networks* (WAN). We have already mentioned the *inline engine* in ADIOS2 whose use requires a different workflow that must first be made available from the openPMD API in order to enable communication within process boundaries.

Some of the optimizations we discussed for this Thesis have explicitly targeted streaming-based workflows. There is technically no reason why optimizations such as buffer reuse across iterations should not be available in disk-based workflows as well. Having already implemented such optimizations within the streaming workflow, efforts should be made to investigate possible generalizations, resulting in benefits also for disk-based workflows.

During our evaluation of streaming IO, it has become increasingly apparent that manually launching two or even more concurrently executing applications cannot be a permanent solution. Classical batch systems have largely been designed with execution of single, i.e. tightly coupled applications in mind as a first-class use case. While it is in general possible to use batch-systems for use cases such as ours, these batch scripts show to be largely non-portable and error-prone with regards to resource allocation. A candidate for automatized creation of loosely coupled workflows with the streaming-aware openPMD API is DASK [10] whose task-graph based approach at modeling task parallelism has led to wide-spread use in the scientific community. To this end, we must integrate the openPMD API into the DASK ecosystem as a possible link between loosely coupled applications managed within this framework.

We conclude that we have successfully loosely coupled two scientific HPC applications to make use of modern interconnect hardware for scalable IO. We hope that this will allow for the creation of streaming workflows for physical simulations. We observe numerous opportunities for continued work and research on the fundamentals laid out in this Thesis.

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